

Report on the SIESTA epidemiology tool

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1. INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this document is to provide information on the work developed within the Work Package 14 (WP14) of the EOSC project SIESTA. The WP14's objectives, methodology and organisation are detailed below. However, it is important to include here some words on the main motivation of the case study and its significance for the scientific community of epidemic modeling.

1.1. MOTIVATION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PILOT CASE

WP14's research line revolves around computational epidemiology and public health management. As the recent COVID-19 pandemic has shown, this is a topic in which the access to high quality data can be crucial. The most delicate information is usually related to the health status of individuals, their disease clinical progression and the spatio-temporal evolution of the epidemic at population level. This data traditionally is transferred from hospitals and other health facilities to public agencies that, such as Santé Publique in France or Instituto de Salud Carlos III in Spain, collect the data, process it and, finally, release it to researchers and the general public. There are alternative ways to estimate prevalence levels of infectious diseases in a population, and here, we implement one based on participatory science. These are systems in which volunteers, who act as probes of the population, report their health status and health-related behavior weekly. We explore here the connection of these systems to data spaces as the EOSC SIESTA platform.

Besides the information on the disease prevalence, there are many other data types that are fundamental for computational epidemiology and the forecasting of disease propagation patterns. These include detailed information on the demographic composition of the population and their behavior, such as mobility, contacts and time use. WP14 boards this second question by demonstrating how to build synthetic populations for France, Italy and Spain, corresponding to the data available in official sources regarding population demography, households characteristics, mobility patterns and time use. We then build disease spreading data-driven simulators fed with this information and make them available for EOSC SIESTA users. In this way, researchers and stakeholders can access state-of-the-art epidemic simulation results without having to access, buy or collect and process all the microscopic datasets needed, which are ruled by privacy and confidentiality requirements. The methods developed to generate the synthetic populations and the epidemic models are generic and can be applied in any other European country. Not only that, the implementation in a data space of computational epidemiology tools as the ones developed here have the potential to open their use to stakeholders as public health authorities.

1.2. STATE OF THE ART

Population health status, demographic characteristics, residence location and human mobility data are fundamental to study epidemic spreading patterns. Pathogens use infected humans as vehicles and mobility networks strongly impact spatio-temporal patterns of disease spread. Besides, models need to be integrated with epidemiological

data, both at the population and individual level from surveillance systems in order to calibrate its parameters.

The SIESTA WP14 leverage on previous systems such as Influenzanet (<https://influenzanet.info>), a network of Web-based platforms for participatory surveillance established in several European countries (Italy, Belgium, the Netherlands, France, Switzerland, Ireland, Portugal, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, United Kingdom and Ireland) and also from platforms as Gleanviz (<https://www.gleanviz.org>), the EU project Stamina (<https://stamina-project.eu/>) and PANDEM-2 (<https://pandem-2.eu/>), whose goal was to sowing the seeds for technology-based decision-making tools to build pandemic preparedness and maximise outbreak response efforts.

1.3. SIESTA PERSONAS

In WP14 the SIESTA personas involved are the **data rights holder**, the **data user** and the **platform operator**. In this section we assume that the SIESTA data rights holder is working in a different institute than the data user; if they were working in the same institution, they could share data directly without the need of the SIESTA platform.

The **data rights holder** decides under which conditions the datasets, such as the aggregated data from EpidemiRadar, can be shared, with whom, and they are responsible for initiating the data transfer. It is also the responsibility of the **data rights holder** to organize the data according to privacy and confidentiality standards, to preserve patients' sensitive information present in their electronic health records and ensure the correct data management, in accordance with the DMP.

The **platform operator** and the **data rights holder** have to settle on a way to transfer the data. We assume in the following that the data rights holder is affiliated to a European research institution and that the **SIESTA platform operator** is working at the computer center that hosts the SIESTA platform. The data is originally stored on a system in the research institution and gets transferred to the secure SIESTA storage system.

Uploading is in general considered as "sending data away" over the network, whereas downloading is "receiving data". Specifically for data ingestion into SIESTA, uploading can be considered as the situation where the data rights holder delivers the data at the SIESTA central storage. For the data transfer into SIESTA we refer to this as "uploading" in case the platform operator creates an account on the SIESTA platform for the data rights holder and if the latter initiates and controls the transfer. We refer to this as "downloading" if the data rights holder creates an account for the platform operator on their institutional system, and if the latter initiates and controls the transfer. In neither case is the data user involved in the data transfer.

The **data user persona** in WP14 represents epidemiologists, epidemic modellers, public health professionals, teachers, students or private citizens that aim to answer a specific research question in epidemiology using the data and tools generated by WP14, like the data collected from EpidemiRadar in Task14.1 and/or the epidemic models developed in Task 14.2 based on the synthetic populations of Italy, Spain and France. These data and tools are made available for analysis on the SIESTA platform, under certain

conditions highlighted in the next sections specific to both tasks. Upon registration, the data user persona can receive an account from the platform operator, access the SIESTA platform and download the aggregated privacy preserving data stored for EpidemiRadar to inform epidemic models of their own, or use it to inform the epidemic models developed by WP14 provided on the SIESTA platform. Once satisfied with the epidemic modeling, the data user persona will be able to download the simulation outcomes in a private way, i.e. without sharing these results with other data users. All simulation results will be stored for a limited amount of time to prevent massive memory usage and will be visible to the platform operator for sake of maintenance. In no way the results of the simulations will be visible to other data users.

2. WORK PACKAGE ORGANIZATION AND TASK STRUCTURE

The objectives of the WP14 are:

- To collect data required for epidemiological models (population, mobility, surveillance, etc.) from standard sources public and private.
- To develop the tools to share participatory surveillance systems data within the SIESTA framework.
- To build the models needed to study propagation scenarios of generic infectious diseases using these data.
- To develop a user-friendly interface that will allow the access of expert and non-expert users to the models.

For attaining them, the work to develop in WP14 was organised in three tasks:

- Task 14.1 – Participatory surveillance data collection. This task includes the development of a participatory online platform in such a way that users can freely inform on their health status regarding respiratory symptoms. The target is initially Spain, with sister tools already in production in other EU countries. The idea was to consider the integration of the outputs of such platforms in the EOSC (SIESTA) data space. The results of this task are detailed in Section 3 of this document.
- Task 14.2 – Data-driven simulators. The aim of this task is the development of data-driven simulators for the propagation of infectious diseases. There are two main frameworks for modelling such propagation: agent-based and metapopulation models, depending on the minimal scale of the simulator. In the case of agent-based models, the unit is individuals and synthetic populations are built out of official statistics. Metapopulation models, on the other hand, have as minimal units the populations of administrative areas (e.g., municipalities). In this task, models of both frameworks have been developed for France, Italy and Spain, and they have been integrated in the EOSC (SIESTA) platform. The work performed and the results are described in Section 4.
- Task 14.3 – User interface. This last task has as main objective the development of a graphical interface for the users to build epidemic models, adapted to different infectious diseases, to communicate with the tools developed in Task 14.2. In addition, users can launch the simulations, check when they are over, visualise some simplified outputs and download the simulation results locally. The characteristics of the graphical interface and the work in its development are described in Section 5 of this deliverable.

3. PARTICIPATORY SURVEILLANCE PLATFORM

3.1. INTRODUCTION

Participatory disease surveillance platforms are systems in which people can register and inform on their health on a weekly basis. Such participation is absolutely voluntary, all users can register, unregister and delete their personal data at any moment. The idea is that the volunteers act as probes on the health situation of the population regarding influenza-like-illness (ILI). In exchange, the platform generates situation maps on the extension of disease propagation and epidemic curves to track the quasi-real time ongoing of the epidemic. Similar platforms have been launched in different EU countries. In particular, the Italian one and the European network of Influenzanet are managed from the ISI Foundation, which is a partner in this WP and has facilitated the development of the Spanish platform called *epidemiradar*. It is important to stress that in this case the objective was not only to extend this technology to an extra country, but to explore the integration of the results in a common EOSC (SIESTA) data space.

Traditional surveillance of influenza and other respiratory diseases such as COVID mainly relies on syndromic surveillance from sentinel general practitioners (GP) networks. A small fraction of the cases arriving at clinics and hospitals are analysed genetically to determine the particular strain of the pathogen and reported at regional or national scale. This method is useful, but it has several drawbacks. The cases arriving at GPs and hospitals are usually those with the worst symptoms and are biased toward vulnerable age groups, either children or elderly people, which may have worse prognosis and require treatment. In the case of influenza or COVID, most of the infected people, without further conditions, stay at home and do not report to the health centers. A second issue is that the symptoms tend to look more severe, since only the worst cases are registered. These biases are usually corrected afterwards with other investigations such as seroprevalence surveys, but they can distort the current assessment needed for intervention on seasonal and emerging diseases.

An interesting complement to this partial view is brought by participatory surveillance. The tool *epidemiradar* follows on a European effort to develop epidemic participatory platforms as, for example, *Influweb* (influweb.it) and *Flusurvey* (flusurvey.net), established in Italy and the UK since 2009. In particular, *Flusurvey* allowed for a reevaluation of the ILI case numbers and the lethality estimation of the global pandemic 2009 H1N1. *Epidemiradar* integrates as well in this network. Following the SIESTA's timeline, *Epidemiradar* is already public and can be access from:

<https://epidemiradar.es/>

3.2. PLATFORM STRUCTURE

The objectives of the platform are:

- Monitoring COVID and influenza-like illness (ILI) activity with the help of volunteers via the internet. Unlike the traditional sentinel network system composed by hospital and primary health practitioners, Epidemiradar collects its data directly from the population. This creates a rapid and flexible monitoring system.
- Contributing to a uniform data collection approach across several European countries (Influenzanet partners), allowing for direct comparison of COVID disease rates and, more generally, ILI across countries.
- Providing additional information on the geographic and demographic distribution of ILI symptoms.
- Facilitating the relationship between infections and potential environmental risk factors.
- Characterising the uptake of COVID and influenza vaccination.
- Testing the integration of Influenzanet platforms in an open data space as the EOSC (SIESTA) one.

Target population

Study participants can be anyone living in Spain and aged 18 or older. Participants will also be able to complete questionnaires for their underage dependents (children) if they wish. Collecting information about children (through their parents or guardians) provides useful information on the spread of childhood infectious diseases such as bronchiolitis.

The inclusion criteria are, therefore:

1. Read and accept the informed consent form, indicating that you understand the purpose of the study and are willing to participate in the online survey.
2. Be a resident of Spain and over 18 years of age.

There are no exclusion criteria, except for not meeting either of these two requirements. There are no sample size targets; the larger the sample size, the more accurate the results.

Participant Withdrawal

Each participant may withdraw from the study at any time and for any reason. Participants may decline further participation at any time after registration if they do not complete the online questionnaire and/or unsubscribe. Furthermore, it is not mandatory to always complete the weekly questionnaire.

Data Collected

Data is collected for research purposes only. Upon registering for the study through the website, participants complete an intake questionnaire containing questions about:

- Gender;
- Month and year of birth;

- Zip code;
- Main daily activity (e.g., full-time job, student, etc.);
- Higher education (yes/no);
- Average number of social contacts per day;
- Number of people living in the household;
- Number of children attending daycare/school;
- Main mode of transportation;
- Information about possible chronic illnesses and allergies;
- Information about influenza vaccinations in the past year;
- Pregnancy;
- Smoking status;
- Information about pets;
- Possible previous episodes of ILI or COVID-19.

After completing this intake questionnaire, participants receive an email each week with a secure link to a symptom questionnaire. This questionnaire asks participants if they have had any symptoms during the past week and, if so, which ones among a list of respiratory and systemic symptoms: e.g. runny nose, cough, sneezing, high temperature, etc. It is important to complete the questionnaire even if a participant is asymptomatic. If this is the case, it takes about 30 seconds to answer the questions; if symptoms are present, it takes about 3 to 5 minutes. The symptoms questionnaire contains questions about:

- Experienced one or more of the following signs and symptoms (e.g., cough, runny nose, fever, headache, etc.);
- Onset of symptoms;
- Did the signs and symptoms go away? If so, when?
- Possible information about fever;
- Sought medical help for the signs and symptoms experienced;
- Took medication for the signs and symptoms experienced;
- Missed school/work due to the signs and symptoms experienced;
- Whether Covid-19 tests were performed.

Once or twice every season, participants receive a vaccination questionnaire. This questionnaire asks if they have been vaccinated against COVID and the flu. It takes between 2 and 5 minutes to complete. The questionnaire includes:

- Number of doses;
- Brand of vaccine;
- Date of vaccination(s);
- Reasons for vaccination;
- Reasons against vaccinations;
- Main side effects;

Platform and Data Security Details

The system enables electronic survey studies. The platform is developed based on experience with the existing InfluenzaNet system, which has actively contributed to research and monitoring the spread of influenza for years. The primary goal was to build a sustainable and scalable system. The technical concept of the system is to run multiple parallel studies along with different front-end clients and associated

applications that are suitable for the study. Unlike many commercial solutions, the system is open-source licensed to meet the independence, transparency, and security requirements of operating institutions and to facilitate further development and adaptation to new and future requirements.

User Authentication

For longitudinal studies, it is necessary to track the progress of a participant's responses throughout the study. The course of the study may also differ for different participants, depending on previous responses and events. For this to be possible, each participant must be authenticated in the system before being able to submit responses.

Identification is done on the epidemiradar.es web app using a username and password in a web browser. Authentication data is stored separately from study data: data elements for user identification are encrypted into a participant ID, which cannot be reconstructed without a key (for example, to separate personal data, such as email addresses, from health data). A user's participant ID is unique to each study by default, but can be configured to be identical across all studies if needed. The database is split into two, and two different administrators are designated for each database:

- Study database: database-admin: Individuals with full access to participant responses, survey definition, etc.
- User database: database-admin: Individuals with full access to account data and records. No study information or related data is stored here.

Even if the same person holds both roles, this person cannot make a reference between the participant ID (responses) and the email address. State-of-the-art encryption methods are used to ensure this. The encryption keys used in the system are part of the application administrator (person with control over the application configuration, including defining the global part of the encryption key). Researchers in charge of analysing and modeling the data cannot have such access.

Backend Services

The survey system consists of several services that communicate with each other via gRPC. Individual services can be scaled horizontally by connecting a suitable load-balancing proxy in front of them. To deploy, manage, and scale the services, Docker and Kubernetes have been successfully tested, but other configurations are also possible.

From the outside, the system must be accessed through an HTTP endpoint. This endpoint will handle the logic surrounding the HTTPS certificate and internally forward HTTP requests to the internal web server. The services will be accessible externally and located on a private network behind a firewall.

Data Storage

A MongoDB instance is used to store data—e.g., participant survey responses, study plan, survey definitions, etc.—the AuthDB (authentication data for users/applications) and StudyDB can technically (but it is not mandatory) be located on different servers.

Generally, these databases will not be accessible from the Internet; they will only be accessible through the private network where the services run or from whitelisted addresses upon authentication. Database backups will be performed at regular intervals.

The database servers will have fast storage to, among other things, shorten read and write processes.

It is estimated that the responses of 1 million participants to a survey represent between 3 and 4 GB of data volume (depending on the survey type). Participants may complete these surveys multiple times. If the system has high population coverage, the database cluster should still be able to index and search the responses. Sufficient memory and computing resources must be available for parallel queries.

3.3. OUTPUT DATA & INTEGRATION TO THE EOSC (SIESTA) PLATFORM

General descriptive results, such as the number of participants, regional distribution, basic demographic data (age, sex), and reported signs and symptoms, will be available on the study website, aggregated by geographic area and k-anonymized to meet common privacy standards. These data will be summarized in tables and frequency charts and will be transferred to the EOSC (SIESTA) platform. More specific statistical analyses may be performed under the supervision of the principal investigators. The results and analysis methods will be reported through scientific publications that will be available on the website and freely accessible to the public.

The private information at individual level will remain at the IFISC servers, according to the rules approved by the CSIC ethical committee. This descriptive data will also be accessible through the EOSC (SIESTA) platform. As described in D10.1, using software tools developed by WP10, a synthetic data generation approach has proven high utility at reproducing studies based on electronic health records collected by the Italian homologous platform of Epidemiradar, from Task 14.1. This technique will be considered in the course of the project as a possible way to share individual level differentially private synthetic data with data users on the EOSC (SIESTA) platform.

3.4. LAUNCHING AND PUBLIC CAMPAIGNS

The platform is ready, it can be accessed through the link:

<https://epidemiradar.es>

It is now undergoing tests to ensure that the surveys are performed according to the processes explained above. The idea is to launch the site officially at the beginning of the next influenza season in September. We will combine social media campaigns with standard press releases using the CSIC and UIB press services. We will count as well with the involvement of the CSIC PTI Salud Global, which is a group created in CSIC during the COVID-19 pandemic who gained strong social visibility during that period.

3.5. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The description of the epidemiradar platform and the detailed questionnaires were submitted to the consideration of the Ethical Committee of CSIC in April 2024. There were a good number of iterations with the Committee to ensure the necessity, pertinence and usefulness of every question in the surveys. The Committee also requested several measures to complete the information provided to the users in the description of the platform, the request of informed consent, the custody of the private information and the data life cycle, including the data deletion policies. Finally, the Committee gave its approval in December 2024.

Here it is important to describe the main points upon which this approval was granted:

- The data collection is done by seasons.
- Users **freely** register and unregister at any moment.
- In case of unregistering, all the personal data identifying such user is deleted.
- Before registration, the users **must read and accept** an **informed consent document** (Annex I) that contains the description of the platform, its objectives, the treatment of the data and their rights to request the information about them and the deletion of all the personal data at any moment.
- The demographic data collected has as purpose the correction of biases in the population sampling and in the prevalence estimation taking as basis the official data from the National Statistics Office (INE).
- All the results will be shown aggregated at geographical scales of provinces/municipalities employing differential privacy tools as Anjana, to avoid any potential unmasking of single users' patterns.
- The minimum number of participants to show results in a geographical area is set at 5.
- The personal data of individuals are stored in a separate server and its only purpose is to contact them for the surveys.
- The persons responsible for the data treatment and their contacts are in the hands of the Ethical Committee.

4. DATA-DRIVEN SIMULATORS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this section is to describe the advances done regarding the Task 14.2, the data-driven simulation tools developed, the data that they need, how it was collected, processed and integrated. The idea is that the users of the space ESOC (SIESTA) can access these epidemic simulation platform, design their own epidemic model in a graphical way (see section 5), run the data-driven models and obtain results showing the disease propagation patterns in France, Italy and Spain, with the hope that this can be generalised later to all the EU countries. All this is done without the need of a direct access to the data, even though the synthetic populations will be publicly available (under CC-BY licence).

The first ingredient is the building of synthetic populations for the three countries. The input data to build the synthetic populations from the statistical offices and other sources are different for each country and require separate processing. Still, the final synthetic populations have the same data structure to be used in the simulators. The models are described afterwards and, finally, we will detail the outputs. The authentication of the users is done across the platform managed through Keycloak, an open-source identity and access management solution that is deployed within Kubernetes.

4.2. DESCRIPTION OF INPUT DATA

4.2.1. France

The synthetic French population is constructed using four main sources of data: demographic surveys from the National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE), microdata provided by Progedo—a French public data infrastructure—, the national building database (BDND), and datasets from the Ministry of National Education.

National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE)

Based on census data, INSEE produces city-level distributions: the number of households by type, the age, sex, socio-professional categories of the reference person according to household type, the number of children by age of the reference person, and the main activity (employed, student, inactive) by age. INSEE also provides data on the number of individuals living in a given municipality and working or studying in another.

Next and for each dataset, we include a brief description. Detailed tables with the variables considered can be found in Annex A. We have considered:

- Municipalities and “arrondissements”. For each municipality or district (arrondissements), we obtain the geographical limits and the number of householdhouseholds.

- Households characteristics in each geographical unit. This includes
 - Type: abundance of households with single person, couple, couples with children, etc.
 - Age distribution of individuals by role in the household, including the reference person.
 - Distribution of household sizes by characteristics of the reference individual.
 - Distributions of the age of the partner, if he/she exists.
 - Information on the distribution of employment properties: students, workers, inactive by age, as well as the categories of the jobs of the workers.
 - Commuting fluxes by age between the geographical units.

National Building Database (BDND)

The National Building Database provides a comprehensive dataset of all buildings in France. For each building, the database includes: its geometry (as a multipolygon), surface area, geographic location (longitude and latitude), number of floors, number of housing units, and nearby points of interest (such as schools, shops, medical practices, hospitals, post offices, etc.).

SIRET Database

The SIRET database contains all enterprises buildings in France, along with their geographic location and the number of employees they host (reported in size brackets).

Ministry of National Education dataset

This database includes a list of primary, secondary, and higher education institutions, along with their geographic location and the number of enrolled students.

Microdata from Progedo

We used a microdata sample (i.e., an anonymized subset of the household population) that includes the age of the reference person and the age of their partner.

4.2.2. Italy

The generation of the synthetic population of Italy relies on data from the Italian National Institute of Statistics (ISTAT). The data extracted from ISTAT databases provide information on age and sex of the population as well as the number of households by size at census tract level; household types and size distribution by regional repartition, professional condition by municipality and origin-destination mobility of commuting by census tract, number of employees and local units of active enterprises at municipal level by economic sector.

We provide now a brief description of the datasets used, with detailed tables of the variables in Annex A below.

Census Tracts

This dataset provides information on the 2021 Permanent Census of Population and Housing. It includes detailed information at sub-municipal levels. The data covers

population demographics (e.g., gender, age, citizenship, education, and employment), family structures, housing (occupied and unoccupied), and residential buildings. Special census sections for homeless individuals and disputed areas are included. This dataset is employed for the generation of the synthetic households and their geographical allocation. It provides the age pyramid and the distribution of the size of the household in a given census tract.

Households microdata

This dataset pertains to the 14th General Census of Population and Housing in Italy, conducted on 21 October 2001. It represents approximately 1% of the resident population (approximately 610,000 individuals across 218,000 households). Each record corresponds to an individual within a household, providing information on gender and age grouped into 5-year age groups (with ages 100 and above included in the final groups). All members of each household are included in the dataset, and each household is uniquely identified by a sequence code. Additionally, households are categorized geographically into five regions: North West, North East, Centre, South, and Islands, corresponding to the NUTS 1 classification by Eurostat.

This dataset is used to generate synthetic household configurations to match the overall macro-regional distribution of household types. Each household type is defined as an unordered sequence of individuals, categorized by age and sex, who share a household.

Local Units of Active Enterprises

The dataset provides the number of employees and local units of companies active in Italy, broken down by economic sector according to the [ATECO 2007 classification](#). The data, updated to 2022, are available on an annual basis and include information ranging from mineral extraction and manufacturing activities to the production of foodstuffs, textiles and other sectors. It is possible to analyse the annual average values of employees per local unit and the number of local units for each sector. This dataset is used to identify the destinations of the employed population.

Professional Condition Distribution by Municipality

The dataset provides a detailed breakdown of the professional and non-professional conditions of the resident population at municipality level as of the year 2022. It categorizes individuals by age groups (15-24, 25-49, 50-64, 65+) and distinguishes between those in the labor force (employed and seeking employment) and those outside the labor force (pensioners, students, homemakers, and others). The data collects the distribution of employment, unemployment, and non-work-related statuses across different age groups, offering insights into the region's workforce composition and demographic trends. This dataset is used to identify the professional status of the population, establishing if the agent is employed, a student or unemployed (including those that do not belong to the labor force in this category).

Employment Distribution by Economic Sector and Municipality

The dataset provides detailed information on the distribution of employed individuals aged 15 and older as of the year 2021, across various economic sectors in Italy. It is organized in specific municipalities. The data includes employment figures across

sectors like agriculture, industry, commerce, transport, financial services, and other activities, offering a comprehensive view of economic activity at both macro and micro levels. This dataset is used to identify the profession of the employed population.

Daily Commuting for Study or Work by Municipality

The dataset provides an annual overview of the daily commuting patterns of the resident population at census tract level, for the years 2018 and 2019. It categorizes movements based on the purpose (study or work), gender (male, female, total), and destination (within the same municipality of residence or outside it). This dataset is used to identify the destination of each agent, given that they have been identified as students or employed.

4.2.3. Spain

The generation of the synthetic population of Spain relies on three main data sources: cadastral data, OpenStreetMap (OSM) data, and demographic and mobility statistics from the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE). These datasets are instrumental in calibrating the synthetic population with realistic distributions and statistical properties, such as household composition, age structure, and spatial mobility behavior.

As above, we include next a brief description of the data used. Detailed tables with the considered variables and pseudo-codes can be found in Annex A.

CADASTRAL DATA (INSPIRE)

The first dataset used is the [INSPIRE](#)-compliant cadastral data, which was obtained from the Spanish cadastre via its ATOM feed service. This dataset is crucial for two main reasons:

1. It allows us to assign each individual to a specific dwelling.
2. It enables the identification of buildings where key activities (work, study, healthcare, etc.) take place.

Additionally, the dataset provides the constructed area for each building, which is valuable for subsequent steps such as determining building usage and modeling disease transmission rates within buildings.

Although the INSPIRE cadastral data is structured into three layers (Addresses, Parcels, and Buildings) only the Buildings layer is used in this work, as it contains all the necessary spatial and structural information. Using Python along with standard web data handling libraries (requests, zipfile, and bs4), we downloaded the building data for all Spanish municipalities, excluding the provinces of Navarra and the Basque Country. These regions manage their cadastral data independently, and their data will be collected separately from their respective official sources.

OPENSTREETMAP (OSM) DATA

The second major source is [OpenStreetMap](#), from which we obtained detailed data for Spain and the Canary Islands. Compared to the cadastral data, OSM provides a

significantly richer classification of building types. While INSPIRE categorizes buildings into six broad categories (agricultural, industrial, office, retail, public services, and residential), OSM offers a much more granular taxonomy, including:

- Public facilities (e.g., government offices, police stations);
- Health services (e.g., hospitals, pharmacies);
- Commercial establishments (e.g., restaurants, hotels, supermarkets, banks, retail shops);
- Recreational and other specialized buildings.

This enhanced level of detail is essential for our model, as it enables the definition of realistic daily schedules for synthetic individuals such as where they go to work, study, shop, exercise, or engage in leisure activities.

We integrate the OSM data with the cadastral dataset to produce a comprehensive building dataset, enriched with multiple attributes such as primary use, floor area, functional categorization, and geospatial information.

INE STATISTICAL AND MOBILITY DATA

The final data source is the Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE), from which we obtained detailed demographic and mobility statistics. These include:

1. Population and Dwelling Data: Provides population figures from 2021 for all Spanish municipalities. For municipalities with more than 2,000 inhabitants, the data includes the number of dwellings and identifies how many of them are unoccupied
2. Microdata: We use three types of microdata: individual-level data, household data, and data from the Encuesta de Población Activa (EPA), Spain's Labor Force Survey.
 - [Household microdata](#): The microdata used in this study were obtained from the Household Survey conducted by the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE). These data provide detailed, anonymized information at the individual and household level, encompassing a wide range of socioeconomic variables. Key attributes include household composition, age, gender, education level, employment status, income, and housing conditions, among others. The following table shows the attributes used in our pipeline after preprocessing the input.
 - [Population microdata](#): The microdata used in this study are sourced from the Active Population Survey (EPA). This survey provides detailed information on the labor force characteristics of the Spanish population, including employment status, occupation, education level, and other socioeconomic indicators. The dataset is organized at the individual level, capturing variables such as age, gender, educational attainment, employment situation (employed, unemployed, inactive), and the number of hours worked. The following table shows the attributes used in our pipeline after preprocessing the input.

3. Mobility Data: Recent INE mobility datasets provide two key elements:

- A grid of spatial "cells" that cover the entire country (referred to here as Spain cells)
- Aggregated flows between these cells, which represent mobility patterns across the country. These data are used to model spatial interactions and daily movement patterns of the synthetic population.

4.3. DATA MANAGEMENT LIFECYCLE

4.3.1. France

The precise description of the algorithm to generate the synthetic population is described in Annex B. In a nutshell, the idea is that out of the data it is possible to measure the statistical distributions of the households characteristics per municipality such as type, size, age of the reference individual, activity, jobs, students, etc.

The number of households in each municipality/district is set to match the data. The type, properties of the reference person and of the other residents referring to the age, activity, job, etc, are extracted from the measured distributions. Once all households have been constructed, an address is assigned to each synthetic household by sampling without replacement from the list of residential locations within municipality m .

For an individual working (or studying) in municipality n , a company (or educational institution) is randomly assigned. The probability of selecting a specific company (or institution) is proportional to the ratio between the number of individuals it hosts and the total number of individuals working (or studying) in all companies (or institutions) within municipality n . Educational institutions are further categorized into types—preschool, primary school, middle school, high school, or higher education—depending on the individual’s age.

We report the national distribution of age classes by sex in the synthetic population and compare it to the corresponding INSEE data.

We then compute the average household contact matrix from the synthetic population, which gives the average number of contacts an individual in age class i has with individuals in age class j . If two individuals belong to the same household, this counts as one contact. This matrix is then compared to the one estimated in the study by Béraud

et al. Since the definition of a contact differs between the two datasets, each matrix is renormalised.

4.3.2. Italy

As in France, we divided the generation in two phases: in phase one we assigned individuals to a household and to a geographical position by using the **Census Tract** and **Households microdata** datasets. In phase two, we assigned each individual an occupation using **Local Units of Active Enterprises, Professional Condition Distribution by Municipality, Employment Distribution by Economic Sector and Municipality** and **Daily Commuting for Study or Work by Municipality** datasets.

As a preliminary step, we generate a set of distributions using the input data described in the previous section. These distributions are stored in csv format as intermediate outputs and later used to support the assignment of various attributes to the agents. The distributions generated is:

- **Household type.** From the household microdata we obtained the household type distribution based on the geographical repartition (Eurostat NUTS 1) and the household size. We call this distribution $P(c|r)$ where c is the household type, r the geographical repartition.
- **Age and sex pyramid.** From the age and sex pyramid at municipal level.
- **Professional condition.** From professional conditions in each municipality, we obtained the probability of an agent to be a student, employed or unemployed by age classes of 15-24, 25-49, 50-64, 65+.
- **Source-to-target census tract connections.** The probability distribution of an agent to reach a census tract, given its professional condition (either student or employed) and its origin census tract (that is, the census tract where its household is set in the synthetic population generation phase)
- **Students by schools.** From the students and schools dataset, we obtained the probability of an agent studying in a school given that the agent is a student, its age and the *destination*.
- **Workplace by sector.** From the working status data, we obtained the probability of an agent working in a given economical sector given the municipality they live.

- **Local units.** With data on the number of workers for each local unit by census tract, we obtained the probability of an agent working in a unit given its *working status* and the *destination*.
- **Time usage.** Temporal distribution analysis of mobility patterns, including work/school departure times across weekdays and weekends, with differentiation of daytime and nighttime activity periods to accurately model population movements throughout various time segments.

We then use the distribution of household types and the information on census tracts to assign each agent to a household within a census tract. Before the assignment, each agent is characterized by a sex and an age, and the census tract it belongs to. This includes a series of constraints to reproduce the correlations observed in the data between age, gender, household type and composition. After it, the activity state is provided for the individuals, their type of job if they are workers and the corresponding mobility is assigned. The details are in Annex B.

Finally, we report the errors in the synthetic population at the national, provincial, and census tract levels, providing a detailed analysis of discrepancies in population assignment and demographic characteristics.

Overview on Italian provinces - relative error on population at provincial level (map), by sex and age (histogram on top) and error on household size (histogram on bottom).

On the left side of the figure, the aggregated error in the population is reported. It ranges from -0.5% in Bolzano/Bozen to -0.02% in Lecce and Messina. This percentage is calculated by comparing the population extracted from the census tract, aggregated to the provincial level, with the synthetic population constructed using the method described earlier.

The histograms on the right depict the relative error for individuals by age and sex (on the top), as well as the error in household size assignment (on the bottom). The comparison is made between the census tract data and the synthetic population. The errors in sex and age range from -1.64% for males in class 06 (ages 25–30 years) to 1.46% for females in class 16 (ages 75 years or older). Regarding errors in household

assignment, the heuristic does not produce any significant errors in terms of household size.

In total, the simulation assigns a population of 58.33 million individuals compared to the target of 58.41 million derived from the census data. This results in a relative error of -0.14%.

We now report the errors at census tract level in two urban areas, Rome and Turin, and two rural areas, Alberobello (Bari) and Norcia (Perugia).

Rome - Census tract-level relative errors in the synthetic population, with demographic breakdown by sex and age

Turin - Census tract-level relative errors on population size in the synthetic population (map), with demographic breakdown by sex and age pyramid at the municipal level.

In urban areas, the synthetic population at the census tract level closely matches the target values, with only a few exceptions in certain census tracts. Additionally, the

number of elderly individuals is generally overestimated, but the relative error remains below 5% in all cases. We now plot the errors in rural areas.

Alberobello (Bari) - Census tract-level relative errors in the synthetic population, with demographic breakdown by sex and age

Norcia (Perugia) - Census tract-level relative errors in the synthetic population, with demographic breakdown by sex and age

To provide a clear visualization, the relative error is used on the map to represent the total population discrepancies at the census tract level. For the histogram detailing the errors by sex and age, the absolute error is used to enhance readability and comparability of the data. In rural areas, the sex and age data at the census tract level is largely accurate, with discrepancies limited to a few units across all sex/age types. A slight bias is observed for females aged 75 and older, but this does not exceed 20 units.

Finally, we report the error on the household contact matrix, which we define as the number of cohabitations between individuals of age i and j . To do so, we compare the household data extracted from the microdata and those derived by the algorithm.

Contact matrix errors - on right the data extracted from the synthetic population (on top) and the microdata (on bottom). On the left the relative error between the two.

The two contact matrices (shown on the left-hand side of the plot) exhibit similar qualitative characteristics, particularly the presence of the main diagonal and secondary diagonals characterizing age homophily of contacts and parenting. However, some disparities arise due to differences in the underlying datasets. The microdata, which we used to sample the household type distribution, dates back to 2001, while the census tract data, which provides the number of residents by sex and age, is from 2021. Additionally, the 1% sample of microdata has a different distribution of household sizes and age pyramids compared to the census tract data.

These differences result in some relative errors, particularly for couples of a certain age. Despite these challenges, we successfully reconstructed a key qualitative feature of the contact matrix: the primary and secondary diagonals. More recent data will be integrated when available to overcome the above limitations.

4.3.3. Spain

DATA PROCESSING

As in the previous cases, the details of the algorithm are in Annex B. this is a brief description of the process and the details are in Annex B. We generate a set of distributions using the input data described in the previous section. These distributions

are stored in json format as intermediate outputs and later used to support the assignment of various attributes to the agents. The distributions generated are as follows:

- **Household type.** With the household microdata, we can obtain the household type distribution based on the province code and municipality size.
- **Household size.** With the household microdata, we obtain the household size distribution based on the province code, municipality size and household type.
- **Age.** With the people's microdata, we obtain the age distribution based on province code, municipality size, household type and person id.
- **Sex.** With the people's microdata, we obtain the sex distribution based on province code, municipality size, household type and person id.
- **Activity.** With the people's microdata, we obtain the activity distribution based on province code, municipality size, household type and age.
- **Working sector.** With the EPA microdata, we obtain the working sector distribution based on province code and sex.
- **Working sector per region.** In addition to the previous distribution, we generate an additional one using the building area data for each region. Workers are assigned to specific sectors based on the total area of buildings within each region.
- **Mobility.** With the mobility data, we obtain the probabilities of going from one cell to another.
- **Workplaces:** Probability of working in each building, based on the building's location (INE cell), sector, and area.

We merge the information of the current use of the buildings of the cadastral data, with more details thanks to the OSM data. This allows us to assign a land use to each cadastral parcel. These land uses include residential, working place by type, retailing, leisure services (e.g., restaurants, cinemas, etc) , hospital, schools etc. Once we have the characteristics of the parcels assigned, we focus on the residential areas to assign the households. The process is similar to the one in France and Italy by using the distributions to generate household type, size, age and gender of the members, activity status and jobs.

The following plot is an example of the distribution of the type of households generated in the area of Valladolid (medium size city in the center-North of Spain and capital of the region of Castile and Leon).

Distribution of households by type, using the categories defined by the National Institute of Statistics, based on a total of 165,005 simulated households in the area of Valladolid.

Similarly, this is the distribution of household sizes generated:

Distribution of households according to their size, based on a total of 165,005 simulated households.

For the same population, this is the example of the activity status assigned to the residents:

Distribution of individuals by their main activity, using the categories defined by the National Institute of Statistics, based on a total of 516,366 generated agents.

All these properties match the ones observed in the official statistical data. The next step is to assign a working place to the working individuals and a school/university to the students. To do this, we use the information on mobility flows of the INE. The agents are assigned a destination to match these flows but taking into account the job/student typology of the destination areas (districts, municipalities and groups of municipalities). This is done in such a way that, for example, if a large factory is located in a certain area of a metropolitan area, most of the individuals moving there are working in the industrial sector. This is done for intra and inter province mobility. This dual approach ensures that both demographic factors and spatial-economic characteristics influence the assignment of economic sectors in the synthetic population.

Spatial distribution of individuals by sector of activity in the province of Valladolid. The left panel shows the density of individuals working in sector 2 (industry), while the right panel shows the density for sector 3

(services). Data is aggregated at the cell level, enabling a fine-grained spatial resolution beyond municipal boundaries. Colors represent the number of individuals per cell assigned to each sector, normalized within each map.

4.3.4. Data Storage

From this point on, the information is common to the three countries. Once we have the synthetic population files ready to be included in the platform, the inputs we will have in it to perform the simulations will be as follows:

- **Files with agent information.** These will be in .csv or similar format and will contain the characteristics of each agent. Each agent will be a record, and each characteristic will be an attribute, with numerical and string attributes.
- **Files with building and housing information.** These will be in a geographic format such as Shapefile or GeoJSON and will contain relevant information about each building, such as its geolocation, use, capacity, and area. These attributes are crucial in determining agent behavior within them and the probability of contagion if contacts occur.

All data will be updated periodically based on the update frequency of the various consulted sources. We work with both static data (surveys conducted at specific points in time) and dynamic data, such as cadastral data or census data from each country. The fact that the input data is automatically generated by our own programs and does not depend on third parties means that data loss is not critical, as it can be easily regenerated

4.3.5. Data access

The results provided to the user can be viewed interactively through the available interface. Additionally, the data used in these visualizations can be directly downloaded by the user.

Accessing the dataset and its corresponding outputs involves utilizing this user interface. Each user is granted access via unique and personalized credentials to interact with the simulations and download the resulting outputs. To mitigate conflicts of interest, outputs are not shared among users.

The user interface features simulation examples and a manual to assist users unfamiliar with such tools. Additionally, default parametrizations for pre-existing diseases are available to demonstrate the simulation tool's functionality.

It is important to clarify that while the dataset is integral to generating the simulations and outputs, it is not directly provided to users. Instead, users leverage the platform's tools to work with the dataset indirectly. Furthermore, the platform is open-source and freely accessible to all interested parties.

Accessing the dataset and outputs is straightforward due to the platform's open-source nature. Any individual can create a user account to gain access, without requiring additional tools or actions.

In summary, the following security measures are followed:

- The data included in the platform (synthetic populations) has been completely de-anonymized before inclusion and contains no personal data.
- Regarding the generated outputs, each user, who logs in with their own credentials, can only access the outputs they have generated. Users cannot access the outputs of other users to prevent conflicts of interest.
- user management will rely on user roles and groups. Different roles will be defined (mainly: administrators and basic users). Administrators will have access to the data included on the platform and default users will be able to access only their simulations: the inputs they have used (parametrizations given by default and the ones generated by them) and the generated outputs (at least a certain number of them depending on disk space availability). Outputs generated by other users will remain inaccessible to them.

4.4. DATA-DRIVEN SIMULATION TOOLS

The synthetic populations integrating the epidemic models will offer a wide range of angles to simulate and understand the complexity of infectious disease spread across demographic, spatial and socio-economic homophilies. This approach will allow testing public health interventions targeted on specific settings, demographics or regions and observe the disparate epidemic outcomes they may produce across population groups. In the next section we will describe the epidemic models integrating the synthetic populations.

4.4.1. Agent-based models

Building on the collected spatial data, we developed a contact-based contagion model (defined as the copresence of individuals in the same setting at the same time), in which we simulate the movement of agents among settings of activity within the whole national territory of Spain, France and Italy along the hours of a typical week.

This model is highly configurable, allowing users to define parameters such as the simulation duration (divided into time steps), the time interval between steps (defaulting to 15-minute intervals) and the epidemiological parameters of transmission and disease progression.

This flexibility enables users to simulate a variety of scenarios involving different types of infectious diseases. Additionally, the model supports region-specific simulations (e.g., departments, or provinces) and the implementation of mobility restrictions, such as remote working or the closure of certain building types based on their function.

As inputs to this model, in addition to the generated populations and the corresponding buildings, we also include an additional JSON file containing the previously described parameter settings. Below, we describe this parameterization in detail.

- **Global conditions.** This section defines general settings for the simulation:

- **multirun**. Boolean. Enables running multiple simulations in parallel.
- **run_count**. Integer. Specifies the total number of simulation runs to perform when multirun is enabled.
- **time_step_minutes**. Integer (≥ 0). Duration of each simulation time step in minutes. By default, 15 minutes is assigned.
- **start_date**. Integer (formatted as YYYYMMDD). Specifies the simulation's start date. This value is used to anchor temporal analyses and align model outputs with real-world calendars. By default, simulations commence at 03:45 AM, a time of minimal activity when the highest proportion of agents are located at home.
- **duration_days**. Integer (≥ 0). Specifies the total number of days to simulate. The total number of simulation steps is computed as:

$$total\ steps = \frac{duration\ days \times 24 \times 60}{time\ step\ minutes}$$

This value determines the overall length of the simulation in discrete time steps.

- **applicability_provinces**. List of strings. Region codes specifying the provinces to include in the simulation. When this list is empty, the simulation runs over the entire country without provincial filtering.
- **applicability_cells**. List of strings. Codes of mobility cells to include in the simulation. When this list is empty, the simulation covers all cells in the country without cell-level filtering.
- **state_by_default**. Integer. Code of the default state assigned to all agents outside the filtered provinces or cells.
- **n_max_contacts_step**. Integer (≥ 0). Maximum number of infectious contacts per agent per time step.
- **seasonality**. Dictionary. Contains parameters to modulate the infection capacity based on the time of year using a sinusoidal model. It includes:
 - **enabled**. Boolean. Indicates whether seasonality is applied.
 - **alpha_min**. Float [0, 1]. Defines the minimum scaling factor for infectivity during the summer season. The infectivity follows a sinusoidal curve throughout the year, reaching its minimum at summer (scaled by alpha_min) and peaking at winter (maximum defined by the infectivity values in the states section).

These conditions allow the simulation to be initialized with specific spatial filters and default states. For usability, the interface may include a search tool to select multiple provinces or cells by code or name.

- **Mobility**

- **Daily mobility**. Daily mobility defines the typical movement behavior of agents within the simulation environment, which can vary based on the disease state an agent is in. This mechanism allows the model to simulate different levels of mobility or restrictions for individuals depending on their health status. We parameterize daily mobility using the following attributes for each specific mobility state:

- name: String. Name of the mobility pattern.
- code: Integer. Identifier code for the mobility type.
- visitable_buildings. Dictionary mapping building type codes to probabilities (`prob`) of visiting.

Defined building type codes	
Code	Building type
1	University
2	School
3	High School
4	Hospital
5	Supermarket
6	Hotel
7	Leisure place
8	Restaurant
9	Other
10	Home

- **Journeys.** This subsection is reserved for future implementation to model transportation modes.
- **Initial conditions.** In this section, using the states defined in the “Disease states” section, we parameterize the initial assignment of disease states to the agents. We use the following parameterization:
 - **population.** A dictionary defining the generic probability of assigning each state to an agent. It is defined using:
 - **state.** The state to be assigned.
 - **proportion.** The probability of assigning that state.
 - **seeds:** A dictionary defining specific subsets of agents with a particular parameterization, aimed at assigning infected states in specific regions. It contains the following fields:
 - **state.** The state to assign.
 - **abs_number.** The exact number of agents to assign this state to.
 - **provinces.** A list of province codes where this assignment should be made if the assignment is done at the province level.
 - **cells.** A list of cell codes where this assignment should be made if the assignment is done at the cell level.

- **Spontaneous Transitions.** This section defines the parameters of transition across disease states following the disease clinical progression once infected, hence defining the periods of state permanence of agents. Infectious periods are modeled using a Gamma distribution, while transitions involving a fixed rate (e.g., vaccine assignments) are modeled as stochastic processes based on exponential transition rates where at each time step a Poisson-distributed number of agents is selected from the eligible population and randomly transitioned to the vaccinated state reflecting time-dependent intervention dynamics with probabilistic assignment. The following parameters are used:
 - **id.** Identifier of the defined transition.
 - **source_state.** ID of the state from which the transition starts (as defined in the “Disease states” section).
 - **target_state.** ID of the state to which agents transition.
 - **from_time_step.** Integer: Time step from which the transition begins to apply.
 - **distribution.** Probability distribution used to describe the transition behavior. It includes:
 - **type:** Type of probability distribution to apply (**gamma** or **exponential**).
 - **rate.** Rate parameter, used in the case of an exponential distribution.

- **Infections.** This section defines induced transitions towards infected states driven by infection. These transitions are probabilistic and governed by a binomial distribution, where the probability of infection is determined by the transmission parameter β . Each infection-driven transition is parameterized with the following fields:
 - **source_state:** ID of the health state from which the infectious agent originates (e.g., a susceptible state).
 - **target_state:** ID of the state to which a susceptible agent transitions upon infection (e.g., exposed or infected).
 - **infectiousl_state:** The state considered as infectious (i.e., agents in this state are capable of transmitting the disease).
 - **beta:** Transmission probability. This parameter defines the probability of infection per contact and is used in the binomial distribution to model the likelihood of transmission events.

- **Disease states.** This section defines the set of discrete health states that agents can occupy throughout the simulation. Each state is characterized by clinical, mobility, and epidemiological properties that determine agent behavior, duration in state, and interaction with other components of the model (e.g., infection dynamics and transitions). Each state is defined using the following parameters:
 - **name.** String. The label of the state, e.g., **SUSCEPTIBLE**, **INFECTED**.
 - **id.** Integer. Unique identifier for each state.
 - **type.** String. The type of agent the state applies to (e.g., **HUMAN**).
 - **clinical.** Boolean. Indicates whether the state is clinically detectable (i.e., symptomatic).
 - **hospitalized_prob.** Float [0,1]. Probability that an agent in this state requires hospitalization.

- **max_timesteps_in_state.** Integer [0, Infinity): Maximum number of time steps an agent can remain in this state. States such as **SUSCEPTIBLE** and **RECOVERED** may have indefinite duration (**Infinity**), while **INFECTED** states have finite durations derived from probability distributions (e.g., Gamma).
- **gamma.** Dictionary. When applicable, this field specifies the shape and scale parameters of a Gamma distribution used to model time spent in the state. This allows stochastic assignment of waiting times and is particularly relevant for infectious states.
- **remarks.** String. Descriptive notes or modeling assumptions relevant to the state.
- **mobilities.** Dictionary.
 - **daily.** list. A list of mobility profiles (referenced by mobility ID) with associated probabilities, representing how likely agents in this state are to follow specific movement behaviors.
 - **journeys.** Dictionary. Reserved for future extensions related to long-distance or multi-modal transport.

PIPELINE

In this section, we describe the sequential stages of our agent-based model pipeline. The pipeline comprises the following modules (each of which is detailed in subsequent subsections):

1. **Preprocessor.** This module reformats and cleans the agents' data to improve computational efficiency. It also generates additional derived fields required for downstream analysis and removes any attributes that are not needed for the simulation.
2. **Prior Parametrization.** Responsible for assigning supplementary fields used in the agents' itinerary planning. In this module, we allocate work schedules and days off, default visit locations based on each agent's principal activity region, and other preparatory parameters.
3. **Day Simulator.** Invoked at the start of each simulated day, this module constructs each agent's daily agenda (namely, the sequence of locations to visit and the duration of each visit) based on their assigned mobility profile and activity schedule.
4. **State Updater.** This module provides a set of support functions designed to update the mobility and epidemiological states of agents during each step of the simulation. These functions are used within the Step Simulator module to ensure the agents' status transitions are accurately managed as the simulation progresses, reflecting changes in disease state and location based on model rules and parameterized dynamics.
5. **Step Simulator.** Using the daily agendas, disease-state parameters, and each agent's current health status, this module advances the simulation through discrete time steps, modeling disease transmission events at each step.

PREPROCESSOR

The Preprocessor module performs all necessary data transformations to prepare the inputs for efficient use in the remaining stages of the simulation pipeline. This includes the processing of both building and agent data to ensure consistency, compatibility, and optimized performance.

Building Data Transformation

The geometries of all the geographical units are reprojected to the EPSG:4326 coordinate system. Latitude and longitude coordinates are extracted and stored, enabling distance calculations using a vectorized implementation of the Haversine formula. Each building is assigned a province code, and original building identifiers are replaced with generated integers to enhance computational efficiency. Buildings are also categorized according to their function using the categories defined in the json input.

After all transformations are applied, the provincial building files are merged into a single consolidated file. This is essential because some agents may reside or work in cells located in provinces other than their origin, requiring cross-provincial building assignments.

Agent Data Transformation

For agents, the geospatial coordinates of their residences are determined and dwelling identifiers are converted into generated integers. Workplace references are also mapped to the corresponding building IDs from the processed building dataset.

The module adds new fields to the agent dataset in preparation for further parametrization. These fields will later hold information such as working days, type of working schedule (split or continuous), and working hours. Additionally, for non-working agents, their home is designated as their default activity location.

Outputs

At the end of the preprocessing phase, two key outputs are generated:

- A set of region-specific agent CSV files, each containing updated and structured agent information.
- A single national CSV file consolidating all building data across provinces.

PRIOR PARAMETERIZATION

The Prior Parameterization module is responsible for assigning initial characteristics, behavioral patterns, and activity schedules to all agents in the synthetic population before the simulation begins. This module operates on a region-by-region basis using parallel processing to efficiently handle large populations across multiple geographic regions.

Input Data Structure

The module requires several predefined schedule templates that define different working patterns derived from national employment surveys. These inputs provide comprehensive information about various temporal work arrangements including full-time continuous schedules, part-time patterns, split-shift arrangements, and academic schedules for different educational levels. The schedule data contains statistical distributions of working hours, break patterns, and weekly arrangements that reflect real-world employment conditions. E.g., for the Spanish case, this information is taken from the [Encuestas de uso del tiempo](#) (INE).

Core Parameterization Process

4.4.1.1. Agent Schedule Assignment

The module assigns detailed temporal patterns to each agent through a hierarchical process that addresses different population segments based on their demographic and occupational characteristics:

Healthcare Sector Workers: Agents working in medical facilities receive specialized shift schedules reflecting the 24-hour operational nature of healthcare institutions. The system assigns one of three shift patterns - morning, afternoon, or night shifts. These workers are assigned two consecutive free days per week to maintain realistic coverage patterns. Working schedules are continuous and distributed using the following approximation:

- 40% work from 08:00 to 16:00
- 40% work from 16:00 to 00:00
- 20% work from 00:00 to 08:00

Educational Institution Participants: Young agents within school age ranges are assigned standard academic schedules with consistent daily patterns and weekend breaks. Adolescent students receive age-appropriate schedules, while university-level students are given more varied schedules based on higher education survey data that includes both continuous and split-session academic patterns.

- Agents aged between 3 and 11 years inclusive are assigned a fixed school schedule running Monday through Friday, from 09:00 to 16:00.
- Agents aged 12 to 17 years inclusive, whose main activity building is a high school, are assigned schedules from Monday to Friday, 08:00 to 14:00.
- University students and staff are assigned schedules that exclude weekends, which are set as fixed free days. Working hours are assigned following survey data.

General Working Population: Adult agents with employment assignments receive schedules through a probabilistic process that distributes three main temporal patterns: full-time continuous work, part-time arrangements, and full-time split schedules. The distribution probabilities are derived from national labor force statistics to ensure realistic representation of employment patterns.

- Continuous schedules have fixed durations of 8 hours for full-time and 4 hours for part-time workers.
- Split-shift schedules comprise two shifts per day: the first lasting between 4 and 5 hours, the second between 3 and 4 hours.
- Start times for each agent are randomly assigned in accordance with hourly employment distributions. E.g. the following datasets are used for the spanish case:
 - [Percentage of employed individuals who are at work at the beginning of each hour, relative to the total employed population.](#)
 - [Percentage of people who are working at the beginning of each hour relative to the total number of employed individuals.](#)

Non-Working Demographics: Individuals outside the working age range, unemployed persons, and retirees receive flexible temporal arrangements without fixed obligations, allowing them to engage in discretionary daily activities.

4.4.1.2. Default Institution Assignment

The system systematically assigns accessible locations to each agent across multiple facility categories using geographic and demographic constraints:

Educational Infrastructure: Young agents are assigned to appropriate educational facilities based on their age group and geographic proximity. The assignment ensures that students have designated institutions within reasonable distances from their residences.

- **School Assignment.** Agents with schools as their primary activity locations are assigned a default school according to the following priority:
 - If schools exist within the destination cell, assign the nearest to the agent's household.
 - Otherwise, if no schools are within the destination cell, assign the nearest school located within the home cell.
 - If none are found in the home cell, assign a school randomly from within the province.
- **High School Assignment.** High schools are assigned from among the n closest institutions to the agent's home, where n is a user-defined parameter.
- **Hospital Assignment.** Hospitals are assigned using the same criteria as high schools, selecting from among the n closest facilities.

Commercial and Social Facilities: Each agent is assigned to accessible retail establishments for essential needs, recreational facilities for leisure activities, and

dining establishments. The assignment process considers spatial distribution and ensures diverse options within each agent's activity range.

- **Retailing Assignment.** Each agent is assigned n default supermarkets according to the following procedure:
 - Choose supermarkets within the destination cell. If more than 16 options exist, assign randomly; otherwise, assign the nearest n supermarkets to the agent's home.
 - If fewer than n supermarkets are available in the destination cell, assign the remaining from those located within the origin cell.
 - If still insufficient, assign remaining supermarkets randomly from within the province.
- **Leisure Place Assignment.** Leisure facility assignment follows the same methodology as supermarkets.
- **Restaurant Assignment.** Restaurant assignments follow the same methodology as supermarkets.

Initial Health State Assignment

Each agent's initial epidemiological state is assigned based on user-provided data. The user can specify either the initial probability for each state or the exact number of agents in a given state. Assignments may be geographically restricted to specific provinces or spatial cells, while agents outside these regions receive a default state.

4.4.1.3. Family Structure Identification

The system creates comprehensive household composition mappings by identifying adults who share residences with younger family members. This process first determines which households contain children, then flags adults in these residences with indicators that influence their mobility patterns and daily activity constraints. This identification enables modeling of coordinated family movements, education-related trips, and childcare responsibilities that significantly impact adult schedules and location choices.

Outputs

At the end of the module execution, two key outputs are generated:

- A set of region-specific CSV files containing structured population matrices, including detailed agent profiles, schedules, institution assignments, and initial health states.
- A set of region-specific CSV files capturing the initial disease states of all agents.

DAY SIMULATOR

This module is responsible for generating a daily agenda for each agent, specifying the locations visited throughout the day. The resulting data is stored in a matrix where each row corresponds to an individual agent and each column represents a discrete simulation time step within the day. The value in each cell of the matrix is the identifier

of the location visited by the agent at that particular time. Consequently, the matrix has as many rows as agents in the synthetic population and as many columns as time steps defined for a simulation day.

The generation of daily agendas is conditioned by the day of the week, allowing the identification of agents for whom the current day is a working day. Each agent is assigned a default mode of transport, which is used to compute the duration of trips between locations. This computation is based on the average speed associated with the transport mode and the distance between the agent's residence and their primary activity location. At present, distances are only used to estimate the duration of the commute between home and the primary activity site.

For other trips throughout the day, travel durations are randomly sampled from discrete probability distributions derived from empirical data in Mobility Surveys. These distributions vary according to the type of origin and destination buildings involved in the trip. Contacts are not simulated during travel periods; instead, a generic travel identifier is assigned to time steps corresponding to an agent in transit.

It is important to note that the number of columns in the output matrix is directly proportional to the number of simulation steps per day, which is defined by the temporal resolution of the model. During each time step, agents are either assigned to a location (identified by a building ID) or, if traveling, assigned a reserved ID value of 0. This ID denotes travel time, which is excluded from contagion modeling.

Daily Trip Assignment and Agenda Generation

The simulation of daily movement patterns begins by assigning a number of trips to each agent. This is done using probability distributions derived from the microdata of the Madrid Mobility Survey, which describe the number of trips typically made by individuals across different age groups. These distributions are used to randomly assign a daily trip count to each agent. To ensure consistency with realistic behavior, certain heuristics are applied:

- Agents who leave their home must be assigned at least two trips to account for their return
- All workers and students (excluding remote workers) are also assigned a minimum of two trips to reflect a typical commuting pattern.

Once the number of trips is determined, a daily agenda is constructed. This agenda is represented as a time-resolved matrix, where each agent is initially assumed to remain at home throughout the day. The agenda is progressively updated by allocating specific activities and movements across the simulation time steps.

For agents scheduled to work or study on a given day, the first trips assigned are the commute to and from their main activity location. These assignments are based on the schedules generated during the parametrization phase. The steps involved in moving between home and the main activity place are marked with a generic identifier indicating the agent is in transit. In the case of agents with only two trips assigned for the day, they are sent back home from work to ensure the day ends at home.

Additional trips, beyond the main commute, are allocated for each agent depending on their assigned number of total trips. For working individuals, these extra trips are scheduled to begin after their workday ends. For non-working agents, the start time of their first trip is determined using distributions that represent the percentage of trips that begin at each hour of the day, also derived from the survey microdata. The destinations of these trips are selected based on behavioral patterns observed in the survey data, subject to several rules: for example, an agent may visit two consecutive places of the same category (e.g., two retail stores), but individuals starting from home must visit a location different from home. Additionally, agents with only two remaining trips cannot be sent home on the penultimate trip to ensure that the day ends at their home.

Once the type of place to be visited in each trip is decided, a specific building is randomly chosen from the set of candidate destinations previously assigned to the agent during the parametrization process. In this way, each agent is assigned a realistic sequence of daily activities, consistent with observed urban mobility behavior.

STATE UPDATER

The State Updater module is responsible for managing changes in agent characteristics at each simulation step, ensuring consistency between health states, mobility behavior, and agent locations. It integrates multiple update mechanisms that act in coordination to reflect the progression of the simulation in both epidemiological and mobility dimensions.

- **State Transitions Based on Probabilistic Models.** At each step, the simulation determines which agents change their health status based on probabilistic transition models. These transitions simulate processes such as vaccination or disease progression and are triggered using predefined rules. Some transitions may exhibit exponential waiting times parameterized with stochastic extractions based on a fixed transition probability, while others involve a timer with duration extracted from a gamma distribution.

For transitions governed by exponential distributions, a step-wise probability is used to decide if the transition occurs. In contrast, transitions defined by gamma distributions are handled differently: the waiting time of an agent in the current state is precomputed and stored at the moment of state entry. The agent then transitions automatically once this duration elapses. This mechanism allows for greater realism in simulating processes with delayed or multi-stage behavior, such as incubation or incubation periods.

- **Infection-Driven State Changes.** In parallel with time-based transitions, each simulation step evaluates which agents, among those currently exposed, become newly infected. This process uses binomial sampling to determine infection events, simulating the stochastic nature of disease transmission. For agents who transition as a result of infection, their new state and the exact timestamp of the transition are recorded in the simulation's state-tracking matrix. The originating state (typically 'exposed') is also stored, providing traceability for infection source classification. This mechanism ensures that the infection

dynamics are accurately represented and aligned with epidemiological parameters.

- **Time-Based State Updates.** Agents occupying states with predefined durations are updated accordingly as time progresses. When the duration expires, the agent transitions to the next designated state. This process involves transferring the planned next state to the active state field and resetting the scheduling for any subsequent transitions. If the newly assigned state also has a finite duration, the expected duration and next state are precomputed. This system ensures that all time-dependent transitions are executed consistently and in line with the simulation clock.
- **Mobility Profile Updates.** When an agent's health status changes, their corresponding mobility behavior may also change. At each simulation step, mobility profiles are reassigned where needed, based on predefined associations between disease states and mobility categories. This allows the simulation to reflect behavioral changes such as isolation, hospitalization, or reduced movement due to symptoms. In cases where no specific mobility is defined for a given health state, a default behavior is applied to maintain continuity.
- **Location Assignment for Mobility-Constrained Agents.** For agents with restricted mobility due to their health condition, the model assigns specific default locations. These locations are selected from a predefined set of visitable places that are permitted under the agent's current mobility profile.

STEP SIMULATOR

This module is responsible for simulating contacts between agents and the resulting transmission events. It relies on the agent agendas (which provide location information for each simulation step) and the functions defined in the **State Updater** module for managing state transitions.

After the simulation is initialized and input datasets are loaded, the model enters a loop that iterates over each simulation step, with the total number of steps defined by the user. During each step, the following operations are performed:

1. **Infectious agent check.** The simulator first checks whether any agents remain capable of transmitting the disease. If no such agents are found, the outbreak is considered extinguished, the simulation stops, and the current results are returned.
2. **Daily agenda generation.** If the step marks the beginning of a new simulation day, a new agenda is generated for all agents to reflect their planned activities.
3. **Location assignment.** Based on the current time and the agents' agendas, the location of each agent is updated accordingly.
4. **Infection simulation.** Potential transmission events are simulated by evaluating contacts between infectious agents and susceptible individuals. The likelihood

of infection is governed by user-defined parameters and implemented through binomial sampling, as described in the **State Updater** module.

5. **Vaccination updates:** Newly vaccinated individuals are assigned, when applicable, using a similar probabilistic approach. Only transitions with an exponential duration distribution are considered in this step.
6. **State updates:** The model updates the epidemiological state of each agent. This includes:
 - Identifying agents whose current state duration has expired and applying the corresponding state transition.
 - For those transitioning into a new state with a finite duration, the duration is assigned and scheduled.
 - Updating the infectivity level of agents based on their new state and the user-defined parameters.
 - Adjusting mobility settings for agents whose state has changed, in accordance with the definitions associated with their new state.

4.4.2. Metapopulation models

To complement the agent-based approach, we employed a metapopulation model designed to simulate the spread of infectious diseases across a spatially structured population. This model partitions the territory into discrete spatial units or *cells* (e.g., municipalities or mobility zones) and simulates intra- and inter-cellular disease dynamics by modeling both local interactions and human mobility between regions.

The core model is a compartmental stochastic model where individuals in each cell are categorized into epidemiological states. The model operates in discrete time steps and updates populations by simulating transitions between compartments and mobility-driven interactions. The population distribution and transitions are governed by:

- **State-specific transition rates**, defining progression through disease stages.
- **Infection rates**, determining the force of infection in each location based on local and incoming infectious individuals.
- **Mobility matrices**, derived from empirical data, describing the probability of individuals traveling between cells.

A key component of the algorithm is the calculation of *effective population sizes* and *force of infection* per cell, which accounts for resident and incoming individuals, weighted by their epidemiological states and mobility intensity. Disease spread results from the aggregation of local and imported risks of infection.

The simulation proceeds in a sequence of well-defined stages:

1. **Effective Population Estimation.** For each cell, an *effective population size* is computed to account not only for residents but also for those temporarily present due to mobility. This is done by adjusting the resident population using intercellular mobility probabilities and a mobility returning rate (τ), following the equations derived in [Balcan et al., Journal of Computational Science 1, 132 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocs.2010.07.002>]. The effective population N_j of cell j incorporates contributions from incoming and outgoing movements, ensuring that transmission dynamics reflect true contact potential.

2. **Force of Infection Calculation.** For each epidemiological link (e.g., from susceptible to exposed), the *force of infection* λ_j is based on:
 - The local and incoming density of infectious individuals.
 - The mobility-adjusted mixing rates.
 - A transmission coefficient β associated with each infection pathway.

The model distinguishes between infectious individuals who remain in their cell and those who travel, applying different formulations to estimate their impact on the force of infection.

3. **State Transition Probabilities.** Using the infection and transition rates, the model computes the probability that individuals in a given state will move to another state during the next time step. These probabilities are then applied using a multinomial sampling approach:
 - For each origin state, probabilities are calculated for all possible transitions (including staying in the current state).
 - A multinomial draw determines how many individuals move to each target state, preserving total population count and introducing stochastic variability.

4. **Population Update.** Once transitions are applied, the model updates the compartment counts in each cell. This includes infections, natural disease progressions (e.g., from infectious to recovered), and movements due to mobility.
5. **Output Generation.** After each time step, the model records key epidemiological indicators such as:
 - **Prevalence** (current number of cases),
 - **Incidence** (new cases),
 - **Attack rate** (proportion affected during a period), normalized per 100,000 population.

These outputs are stored in structured data formats for analysis, including per-cell breakdowns.

4.5. INTEGRATION IN THE SIESTA PLATFORM

The simulation models, covering both agent-based and metapopulation approaches, are being systematically integrated into the platform through containerization using Docker. This process ensures that each model runs in a consistent, isolated environment, making it easier to manage dependencies, scale execution, and maintain reproducibility across different systems. Once containerized, these models are orchestrated by the Kubernetes backend infrastructure.

4.6. OUTPUTS & DATA ACCESS

Include a description here of the data sensitivity level (data behind the synthetic populations) and the access of the users.

Synthetic populations are stochastic instantiations of the Italian, Spanish and French populations at household level, built to match the macroscopic marginal distributions on household sizes, compositions, demographic pyramid, the spatial distribution of labour structure and mobility coupling in space. At this stage of production, any link to real identities from microdata is lost. Some instantiations of the synthetic populations will be published on online repositories marked with digital object identifiers under CC-BY licence.

Microdata used to derive the synthetic populations will not be uploaded on the SIESTA platform, a generator function based on the marginals and crossed distributions used in the building process will allow for stochastic instantiations of equivalent populations, to better account for the multiple possibilities in the population spatial arrangement.

Users will be able to access upon authentication to the user interface for the epidemic model builder and run it on the synthetic population, which will be generated anew at run time. The outcomes of the model will be accessible to the user only in a private manner, to ensure confidentiality of results for both academic or non-academic professionals testing hypotheses and willing to publish their results in scientific venues. Users will be able to download the simulation results, which will be deleted from the platform after a maximum storage time to avoid memory consumption.

5. USER INTERFACE

5.1. INTRODUCTION

The Epidemic Modeling User Interface (UI) is a comprehensive, user-friendly platform designed to empower researchers, public health professionals, and decision-makers to simulate, and analyze epidemic models tailored to a wide range of infectious diseases. Developed as part of Task 14.3, this tool serves as the primary graphical interface for interacting with the simulation and modeling capabilities established in Task 14.2.

The UI facilitates an intuitive workflow that guides users through the process of building custom epidemic models by selecting disease parameters, population characteristics and mobility strategies. Once configured, users can seamlessly launch simulations, monitor their progress, and access real-time feedback on simulation status.

To support rapid interpretation and decision-making, the interface provides simplified visual outputs that summarize key results, such as incidence and prevalence evolution over time and dynamic evolution maps. Additionally, users can download detailed simulation results for further analysis or reporting.

This tool is designed with adaptability and scalability in mind, ensuring it can accommodate a variety of disease scenarios and modeling complexities.

5.2. STRUCTURE AND FUNCTIONALITIES

The Epidemic Modeling User Interface is structured to provide an intuitive experience for users, guiding them through the process of model creation, simulation execution, and results interpretation. The interface is composed of several interconnected modules, each designed to fulfill a specific function within the modeling workflow. Below is an overview of the main components and their functionalities:

Epidemiological Model Builder: A graphical interactive, zoomable interface that enables users to design and configure simulation models—either agent-based or metapopulation—by defining states, transitions, infections, mobility, initial conditions, ... all stored in a human-readable JSON format.

Simulation Manager: A centralized dashboard for launching, monitoring, and controlling simulations, offering tools to start, stop, restart, and download results, as well as direct access to visualization tools for deeper analysis and raw outputs.

Visualization Engine: A dynamic, time-aware mapping tool that displays prevalence and incidence across regions, with interactive features that allow users to explore temporal trends and regional dynamics through linked time series plots.

Backend Integration Layer: A well-structured API designed to bridge the frontend components with the simulation engine.

5.3. IMPLEMENTATION IN THE SIESTA PLATFORM

The implementation of the epidemiological interface is guided by the principles of modularity, usability, and seamless integration with the simulation backend developed in Task 14.2. The interface was built using modern web technologies to ensure

accessibility, responsiveness, and scalability across different platforms and user environments.

The interface follows a client-server architecture, where the frontend handles user interactions and visualization, while the backend manages simulation execution and data processing. Key architectural components include:

- Epidemiological Model Builder Module: An epidemiological model configuration wizard that allows users to define disease parameters, population structures, and interventions.
- Simulation Manager: Real-time feedback on simulation status handling job submission, status tracking, and error reporting as well as enabling users to download raw simulation results
- Visualization Engine: Interactive visualizations, time-series plots, summary statistics, and evolution maps.
- APIs to communicate the web application with the simulation engine

5.3.1 Technology Stack

The interface is developed using the following technologies:

Frontend:

- Nuxt for dynamic component rendering and user interaction
- Epidemiological model design: VueFlow
- Visualization: Leaflet and Highcharts for geospatial maps and interactive charts
- State Management: *pinia package* for managing application state and user sessions
- Styling: material design using Vuetify for a clean, responsive design

Backend:

- Backend Integration: RESTful APIs to communicate with the simulation engine and data space.
- Authentication and authorization: Keycloak, integrated with the global project realm, provides secure user authentication and role-based access control.

5.3.2. User authentication and access control

User login and access management are handled through the project-wide Keycloak realm, ensuring a unified and secure authentication mechanism across all components of the platform. This integration supports:

- Single sign-on (SSO) across project tools
- Role-based access to specific features (manager and researcher)
- Secure token-based session management

LOGIN

5.3.3. Epidemiological model builder

The Epidemiological Model Builder is a powerful, interactive interface that allows users to design and configure the structure and parameters of their simulation models from the ground up. Upon entering the builder, users choose between the simulation paradigms developed in task 14.2: agent-based or metapopulation. This choice tailors the subsequent configuration options to the selected modeling approach. The interface is zoomable and modular, enabling users to visually construct models by adding states (e.g., Susceptible, Infected, Recovered), defining transitions between them, and specifying infection dynamics, mobility patterns, and intervention strategies. Each component is editable through intuitive panels. Once all these inputs are defined, the builder validates the configuration and generates a comprehensive JSON file. This file includes metadata, structured parameter definitions, and is fully compatible with the simulation engines developed in Task 14.2. It can be saved, reused, or shared to ensure reproducibility and transparency in model design.

The builder also includes a comprehensive settings interface with three main tabs: Global Conditions, Mobility, and Initial Conditions. These tabs allow users to fine-tune simulation-wide parameters such as population size, contact rates, movement between regions, and the initial distribution of individuals across states and locations. Users can import existing models or export their current setup for reuse or collaboration. The interface emphasizes clarity and usability, with drag-and-drop elements, contextual tooltips, and real-time validation to ensure model consistency. This makes the Model Builder not only a technical tool but also an educational and collaborative environment for exploring complex epidemiological scenarios.

Settings agents

Global_conditions | Mobility | Initial_conditions

Run Count:

Start Date: Duration Days: Timelstep Minutes:

Seasonality: Enabled Alpha min:

Applicability Regions: Regions: Cells:

Max. Infectious contacts by step:

Global Mobility Reduction Percentage:

Settings (agent-based)

Global_conditions | Mobility | Initial_conditions

Daily agents

Name:

Building type: prob Home 0.8

Building type: prob Supermarket 0.05

Building type: prob Other 0.15

5.3.4. Simulation Manager

The Simulation Manager View serves as the central hub for managing and monitoring epidemiological simulations. It provides users with a clear, organized interface where they can launch new simulations by loading or creating a new epidemiological model, and initiating runs with a single click. Once simulations are underway, users can view real-time status updates—such as queued, running, completed, or failed. Each simulation entry includes intuitive controls to start, stop, or restart the process, giving users full control over the computational workflow.

ID	Descripción	Tipo	Estado	Acciones
<input type="checkbox"/> 9fc334ba-e044-4231-afad-2f862a08eae7	Label Job descriptio	Agents	Scheduled	⏪ ⏩ 📄 🗑️ ⬇️ 👁️
<input type="checkbox"/> a8268af4-51af-44fa-9beb-8898ce9642f5	Label	Agents	Done	⏪ ⏩ 📄 🗑️ ⬇️ 👁️
<input type="checkbox"/> 2aec396a-769f-4371-bf61-f620d365e1bf	Label	Metapopulation	Error	⏪ ⏩ 📄 🗑️ ⬇️ 👁️
<input type="checkbox"/> 397782da-beda-4484-9f52-fc0ce846020e	Label	Agents	Running	⏪ ⏩ 📄 🗑️ ⬇️ 👁️
<input type="checkbox"/> 337c8826-8e74-4ca5-8624-701725bd9012	Label Metapop	Metapopulation	Draft	⏪ ⏩ 📄 🗑️ ⬇️ 👁️

Beyond execution management, the view also facilitates data access and exploration. Users can download raw output files for offline analysis or integration with other external tools. Additionally, each correctly completed simulation includes a direct link to visualization tools, enabling seamless transitions from raw data to interactive charts and dashboards. This integration ensures that users can not only manage simulations efficiently but also derive insights quickly, making the Simulation Manager View a powerful interface for both operational control and scientific exploration.

5.3.5. Visualization Engine

The Visualization Tools interface is designed to provide users with an intuitive and interactive way to explore the spatial and temporal dynamics of disease spread. At its core is a time-aware map that displays either prevalence or incidence across the geographic regions defined in the epidemiological model used in the simulation. Users can play through the simulation timeline to observe how the disease evolves over time,

with color gradients or heatmaps representing the intensity of cases in each region. This dynamic map helps users quickly identify hotspots, emerging trends, and the need of interventions across different areas.

In addition to the map, the tool offers a linked time series view. When a user selects a specific region on the map, a detailed chart appears showing the prevalence or incidence over time for that region. This dual-view approach—spatial and temporal—enables users to drill down into specific areas of interest while maintaining a broader understanding of the overall epidemic landscape.

The visualization tools are tightly integrated with the simulation manager, allowing users to jump directly from a completed simulation to a rich, interactive exploration of its results. This empowers researchers, public health officials, and decision-makers to make data-driven conclusions with clarity and confidence.

5.3.6. Integration API

To support seamless integration between the user-facing interfaces and the computational backend, the platform includes a well-defined API layer that connects the frontend components—such as the Simulation Manager, Visualization Tools, and Model Builder—with the simulation engine backend. This API is responsible for handling all communication related to simulation lifecycle management, model configuration, data retrieval, and result delivery. It exposes endpoints for launching simulations, querying their status, stopping or restarting them, and retrieving raw output files or processed data for visualization.

The API also facilitates the transfer of model definitions created in the Epidemiological Model Builder. When a user configures a model, the frontend serializes it into a structured JSON format and sends it to the backend via the API, where it is validated and prepared for execution. Similarly, the API supports importing existing models and simulation results, enabling a smooth workflow across sessions and users. This API ensures that the platform remains scalable, responsive, and easy to integrate with other tools or external systems.

While the API architecture and endpoints are already in place, its integration is currently undergoing validation in parallel with the evolving backend infrastructure. This ensures that the API will be fully aligned with the system's operational requirements and performance expectations once the backend components reach full stability. This phased approach allows for iterative refinement and robust testing, laying the groundwork for a reliable and scalable simulation workflow.

6. CONCLUSION

The aim of WP14 was to contribute to the EOSC SIESTA data space with an ecosystem of tools related to computational epidemiology. These tools were organized in three main tasks, each providing a particular tool or set of tools. The first one, T14.1, leveraged on the work of the European network Influezanet to deploy a citizen science platform called epidemiradar (<https://epidemiradar.es>) in Spain to monitor the prevalence of respiratory infectious diseases and to study the way to generate a pipeline between these platforms and the EOSC SIESTA dataspace in such a way that the results can be done available to the users along with all the tools developed in SIESTA and AI4EOSC to analyse them. The epidemiradar platform is up and running, and the official launch will take place in the next epidemic season starting in the fall. At that moment, we will check and test the pipeline to the EOSC SIESTA space.

The second task, T14.2, had as goal the generation of epidemic spreading models able to run in France, Italy and Spain, with flexibility enough to be translatable to any other country in Europe. This objective required the development of synthetic populations in the three countries: we did it based on official statistical sources with minimum adaptation for each country. The main difference refers to the block by block housing information that is slightly diverse in the three countries. Another slight difference was detected in the way that the official statistics of each country treats the household information. However, minimum adaptation produced the synthetic populations for the three countries in a standardized way. These populations are the basis for the epidemic spreading models, which with information on the geographical units in each country, can run in all the countries. There are two families of models in computational epidemiology: metapopulation models that operate an intermedium scale between population and individuals and use districts, municipalities or provinces as spatial units. We have developed these models for the three countries and at all the scales from district to province. The second family is agent-based models in which the basic unit is the individual. These models require the full information of the synthetic population (age, gender, family size, residence and work location, mobility and leisure, etc). These agent-based models have been developed for the three countries with common algorithms that only differentiate between countries in the input data.

Finally, the third task, T14.3, had as aim the development of a visual interface to interact with the epidemic models. This has been done using compartments (boxes) to represent the state of the individuals versus the disease and with arrows corresponding the transitions. The parameters (transition and infection rates) are introduced by the user as he/she builds and introduces the disease progression diagram. The tool is ready and it is being now implemented to the SIESTA data space with the development and validation of a communication API.

The objectives of WP14 have been fully attained, while the activity in computational epidemiology, including the fine tuning of the implementation in the SIESTA environment, its tests and the production of research results will continue within WP19.

7. ANNEXES

ANNEX A. DATA TO BUILD THE SYNTHETIC POPULATION

These are the tables with the variables considered per category:

France

Population of municipalities

From <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/5359146> we extract the list of municipalities in France, which will be the basis for the following work, with the number of household in each city. For big cities (Paris, Lyon, Marseille) we consider districts (“arrondissements”).

Municipality	Municipality insee code
Number of household	Number

Household composition

a) Type of Households

From https://catalogue-donnees.insee.fr/fr/catalogue/recherche/DS_RP_MENAGES_COMP, we extract for each municipality the number of households in each city by household type.

Municipality	Municipality INSEE code
Type of household	1: Man alone 2: Woman alone 3: Couple without children 4: Couple with children 5: Man alone with children 6: Woman alone without children 7: Other
Number	Number of Household of type HH in the municipality

c) Age of individuals

From https://catalogue-donnees.insee.fr/fr/catalogue/recherche/DS_RP_MENAGES_COMP, we extract for each municipality the number of a given age, by role in the household.

Municipality	INSEE code
Role	1: Adult in traditional family 2: Adult alone 3: Adult of a couple without children 4: Adult in monoparental family 5: Child of a traditional family 6: Child of a monoparental family

	7: Other
Age classes	M15: Less than 15 yo 15_24: Between 15 and 24 years old 25_39: Between 25 and 39 years old 40_54: Between 40 and 54 years old 55_64: Between 55 and 64 years old 65_79: Between 65 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
Number	Number of individual with role XX in age class AA

d) Age of reference person

From <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/8205233#consulter> (file “**MEN5v1 – Ménages par type détaillé de ménage et âge de la personne de référence**”), we extract for each municipality the number of reference persons of a given age for each household type.

Municipality	INSEE code
Type of HH	1: Man alone 2: Woman alone 3: Couple without children 4: Couple with children 5: Man alone with children 6: Woman alone without children 7: Autre
Age class	M20: Less than 20 yo 20_24: Between 20 and 24 years old 25_39: Between 25 and 39 years old 40_54: Between 40 and 54 years old 55_64: Between 55 and 64 years old 65_79: Between 65 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
Number	Number of reference persone in a household of type HH in age class AA.

d) Size of households

From <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/8205233#consulter> (**MEN4 – Ménages par taille du ménage, sexe et âge de la personne de référence**) we extract for each municipality the number of household with a given size, given the age and the sex of the reference person.

Municipality	INSEE code
Sexe of the reference person	1: Man

	2: Woman
Age of the reference person	M20: Less than 20 yo 20_24: Between 20 and 24 years old 25_29: Between 25 and 29 years old 30_34: Between 30 and 34 years old 35_39: Between 35 and 39 years old 40_44: Between 40 and 44 years old 45_49: Between 45 and 49 years old 50_54: Between 50 and 54 years old 55_59: Between 55 and 59 years old 60_64: Between 60 and 64 years old 65_69: Between 65 and 69 years old 70_74: Between 70 and 74 years old 75_79: Between 75 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
Size of the HH	1 : 1 person 2 : 2 persons 3 : 3 persons 4 : 4 persons 5 : 5 persons 6 : 6 person or more
Number	Number of Household of size NN, with reference person in age class AA and sex SS.

e) Age of the partner

From <https://data.progedo.fr/studies/doi/10.13144/lil-1646> (Microdonnées sur la composition des ménages à l'échelle de la France (2022) : **Statistiques sur les ressources et les conditions de vie.**) we a representative sample of households form the national french population, (each row = one household), with the age of the reference person and the age of the partner.

Age class of partner	Age of the partner M15: Less than 15 yo 15_24: Between 15 and 24 years old 25_39: Between 25 and 39 years old 40_54: Between 40 and 54 years old 55_64: Between 55 and 64 years old 65_79: Between 65 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
Age class of reference person	Age of the reference person M15: Less than 15 yo 15_24: Between 15 and 24 years old 25_39: Between 25 and 39 years old 40_54: Between 40 and 54 years old

	55_64: Between 55 and 64 years old 65_79: Between 65 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
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f) Employment

From <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques/5359146> we extract for each municipality The number of people with a given employment status (Student, worker, inactive) given the age.

Municipality	INSEE Code
Age	15_24: Between 15 and 24 years old 25_39: Between 25 and 39 years old 40_54: Between 40 and 54 years old 55_64: Between 55 and 64 years old 65_79: Between 65 and 79 years old 80P: More than 80 years old
Status	Student Worker Inactive
Number	Number of individuals with status SS and age category CAGE

g) Socio-professional category

Municipality	INSEE Code
Socio-professional category	1: Farmer operator 2: craftsman, salesperson, company director 3: manager, senior intellectual 4: Intermediate profession 5: Employee 6: workman
Number	Number of individual with SPC XX

2) Commuting flux

CODGEO	Code of the home municipality
DCLT	Code of the working municipality
NBFLUX_C21_ACTOCC15P	Number of individuals living in CODGEO and working in DCLT

COMMUNE	INSEE Code of the residential municipality
DCETUF	INSEE Code of the studying municipality
AGEREV10	Age class of the individual (10 age classes) 02 : 0-2 years 03 : 3 years 04 : 4 years 05 : 5 years 06 : 6-10 years 11 : 11-14 years 15 : 15-17 years 18 : 18-24 years 25 : 25-29 years 30 : 30 + years
N	Number of people of age AGEREV10, living in municipality COMMUNE and studying in municipality DCETUF.

SIRET Database

From the siren database (<https://sirene.fr/sirene/public/creation-fichier#localisation-geographie>) we extract the list of workplaces in each municipality. We select the following variables:

Municipality	
siret	Unique id that identifies the workplace. It is composed of 14 digits. The first 9 digits are the “siren”, an id of the enterprise (“Unité légale”). The 5 next digits are the “nc” an intern id.
trancheEffectifsEtablissement	Category of number of people working in the workplace : 0 : between 0 and 2 1 : between 3 and 5 2 : between 6 and 9 3 : between 10 and 19 11 : between 20 and 49 12 : between 50 and 99 21 : between 100 and 199 22 : between 200 and 249 31 : between 250 and 499 32 : between 500 and 999 41 : between 1000 and 1999 42 : between 2000 and 4999

	51 : between 5000 and 9999 52 : more than 10000 53 : more than 10000
coordonneeLambertAbscisseEtablissement	xx position of the workplace
coordonneeLambertOrdonneeEtablissement	yy position of the workplace

Ministry of National Education dataset

a) Schools

Id of the school	Id of school
SIREN_SIRET	SIRET code of the school
Code postal	Code of the municipality (code postal)
Code_commune	Code of the municipality (insee code)
latitude	latitude
longitude	longitude
N	Number of students

Italy

These are the tables with the variables considered per category:

Census Tracts

Name	Type	Description
RIP_GEO	Numeric, integer	Numeric code that uniquely identifies the geographical repartition code, corresponding to the NUTS 1 classification by Eurostat.
PRO_COM	Numeric, integer	Numeric code that uniquely identifies a municipality within the national territory, created by combining the province code (or former province replaced by a metropolitan city) with the municipality's three-digit number.
SEZ21_ID	Numeric, integer	Code that uniquely identifies the census section nationally (concatenation of the PRO_COM code with the 7-digit SEZ field).
P{30-45}	Numeric, integer	Number of males per age class: Key P30: Age class 0-5 Key P31: Age class 5-10 ...

		Key P44: Age class 70-75 Key P45: Age class 75+
P{67-82}	Numeric, integer	Number of female per age group: Key P67: Age class 0-5 Key P68: Age class 5-10 ... Key P81: Age class 70-75 Key P82: Age class 75+
PF{3-8}	Numeric, integer	Number of households per size: Key PF3: Single-person households Key PF4: Households with 2 members Key PF5: Households with 3 members Key PF6: Households with 4 members Key PF7: Households with 5 members Key PF8: Households with 6 or more members

Households microdata

Name	Type	Description
RIP_GEO	Numeric, integer	Numeric code that uniquely identifies the geographical repartition code, a territory corresponding to the NUTS 1 classification by Eurostat.
ID_FAM	Numeric	Household ID
PROGR_IND	Numeric	Progressive index of the individual in the family
SESSO	Categorical	Sex, 0: Male, 1: Female.
ETA_20CL	Categorical, integer	Age of the individual, in 5-years bracket. '01' corresponds to group [0,5) '02' corresponds to group [5,10) ... '19' corresponds to group [95,100) '20' corresponds to group above 100

Spain

INE STATISTICAL AND MOBILITY DATA

Household microdata:

Name	Type	Description
ID VIV	numeric	Household ID
IDQ PV	categorical	Province code
municipality size	categorical	Municipality size categories: '<5000', '5K-20K', '20K-50K', '50K-100K', '100K-500K', '>500K'
household type	categorical	'0': one-person household '1': mother/father alone with child '2': childless couple '3': couple with any children <25 ' '4': couple with all children >25 ' '5': couple with some children <25 and other people '6': childless couple and other people '7': people who don't form a couple '8': other (>1 nucleus)
household size	int	Size of the household (e.g., 1, 2, 3, ...)

Population microdata:

Name	Type	Description
ID VIV	numeric	Household ID
IDQ PV	categorical	Province code
municipality size	categorical	Municipality size categories: '<5000', '5K-20K', '20K-50K', '50K-100K', '100K-500K', '>500K'
household type	categorical	'0': one-person household '1': mother/father alone with child '2': childless couple '3': couple with any children <25 ' '4': couple with all children >25 ' '5': couple with some children <25 and other people '6': childless couple and other people '7': people who don't form a couple '8': other (>1 nucleus)
household size	int	Size of the household (1, 2, 3, ...)
sex	categorical	'0': man '1': woman
age	numeric	Age of the person
activity	categorical	0': 'working', '1': 'stopped', '2': 'studying', '3': 'retired', '4': 'disabled', '5': 'housework', '6': 'Other', '7': 'Not applicable' (people with less than 16 years

ANNEX B. ALGORITHMS TO PROCESS THE DATA TO BUILD THE SYNTHETIC POPULATIONS

These are the algorithms and pseudo-codes to build the synthetic populations in the three countries:

France

Data pre-processing

From INSEE census data, we computed the following distributions for each municipality m :

- $P(\text{Type of household} \mid m)$
- $P(\text{Age of the reference person} \mid \text{Type of household}, m)$
- $P(\text{Size of the Household} \mid \text{Age of reference person}, \text{Sexe of the reference person}, m)$
- $P(\text{Age of child} \mid \text{Type of household}, m)$
- $P(\text{Main activity} \mid \text{Age}, m)$
- $P(\text{Socio-professional category}, m)$
- $P(\text{working in municipality } m \mid \text{living in municipality } n)$
- $P(\text{studying in municipality } m \mid \text{living in municipality } n)$

We merged the national building, SIRET and National Education databases, to get for each building (building, workplace and studying place) the probability for one individual in a given municipality to live/work/study in this building

Algorithm

The following algorithm is applied to each municipality.

For one municipality m .

$$N_{HH,m} \leftarrow \text{Number of household in } m$$

$$C_{HH,m} \leftarrow \text{Number of household in the synthetic population for municipality } m$$

$$C_{HH,m} \leftarrow 0$$

while $C_{HH,m} < N_{HH,m}$:

sample the type of household from $P(\text{Type of household} \mid m)$

sample the age of the reference person from $P(\text{Age of the reference person} \mid \text{Type of household}, m)$

sample the size of the household from $P(\text{Size of the Household} \mid \text{Age of reference person}, \text{Sexe of the reference person}, m)$

Sample the age of the children from $P(\text{Age of child} \mid \text{Type of household}, m)$

Sample the activity (active, student, inactive) of each member of the household from $P(\text{Main activity} \mid \text{Age}, m)$

Sample the SPC of each member from $P(\text{Socio-professional category}, m)$

Depending on the activity of each member, sample the municipality where each member carry its main activity from $P(\text{working in municipality } m \mid \text{living in municipality } n)$ and $P(\text{studying in municipality } m \mid \text{living in municipality } n)$.

Italy

A. Assign agents to households and census tract

This implies that, as preliminary step, for each census tract we extract:

- the number of individuals by age class and sex $n(a, s)$;
- the number of households by size $n(h)$.

To assign agents to households, we use the following procedure:

1. Extract candidate household for census tract:

- Extract a set of household types from the household type distribution:
 - For each household size h , extract $n(h)$ household types c from the distribution $P_h(c|r)$ with replacements, conditioned on the geographical partition r . Ensure that c matches the observed sex and age composition $\{s, a\}$ in the census tract. This refines $P_h(c|r)$ into $P_h(c|\{s, a\}, h, r)$, where $\{s, a\}$ represents the sex and age composition of individuals in the census tract.
- For each h , obtain a sequence of household types: $C_h = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{n(h)}]$.
- Combine all sequences C_h into a single set of household types for the census tract: $C = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N\}$, where N represent the number of unique household types extracted after this procedure.
- Define x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N as the unknown integer variables representing the number of households of each type c_1, c_2, \dots, c_N .

2. Set Up and Solve the System of Equations:

- Construct a system of equations with N variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N , adding constraints based on:
 - Age and sex composition.
 - Household sizes in the census tract.
- Solve for the integer solution of this system.
- If the system is unsolvable, restart the process of extracting household types (Step 3) up to 10 times. Each time, relax the constraints on sex and age, thus transforming the system of equations into a system of inequalities.
- If the algorithm fails after 10 attempts, extract household types from $P_h(c|r)$ while respecting only household sizes, ignoring sex and age constraints.

3. Final Output:

- From the values of x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N in each census tract, determine the households in the census tract.

Example

Let's consider a simplified example:

- **Census Tract Data:**

Census tract has 10 males aged 30–35, 8 females aged 20–25, 6 households of size 2, 3 households of size 3, and 1 household of size 6 or more. Or, according to our convention:

- $n(\text{ages } 30\text{--}35, \text{male}) = m(M07): 10$
- $n(\text{ages } 20\text{--}25, \text{female}) = m(F05): 8.$
- $n(2): 6$
- $n(3): 3$
- $n(6+): 1$
- **Household Type Distribution:**
 - $P_h(c|r)$: Probabilities for household types (e.g. 4x[F16], 5x[M07], 2x[M07,F05], 4x[M07,M07], 1x[M07,F05,F05], 2x[M06,F05,M01]).
- **Process:**
 - Extract $n(2) = 5$ household types for size 2 and $n(3) = 3$ for size 3.
 - Refine $P_h(c|r)$ to match $\{s, a\}$: e.g., $P_h(c|\{s, a\}, h, r)$ prioritize the household types [M07,F05], [M07,M07] and [M07,F05,F05], because they match the available age/sex compositions of the individuals and the sizes of this census tract. Notice that the single households have been excluded together with [M06,F05,M01], because there are no M01 individuals.
 - Extract the candidate household types from $P_h(c|\{s, a\}, h, r)$: extract 5 for $h=2$ and 3 for $h=3$, to match $n(h)$.
 - Solve the system of equations to assign individuals to households.
 - If unsolvable, relax constraints and retry.

B. Assign agents to an activity

Each agent was assigned to a household and, consequently, to a census tract. Through the latter, it is possible to assign a municipality. For each agent, we follow this procedure:

1. **Get a professional activity:**
 - Based on professional condition distribution, agents are categorized as:
 - i. Student
 - ii. Employed
 - iii. Unemployed
 - For unemployed agents, no activity is assigned
 - For students:
 - i. Educational level is assigned (elementary, middle, high school, or university) based on age
 - ii. Activity is designated as "student + educational level"
 - For employed:
 - i. Activity is assigned according to the economic sector
 - The agent's professional activity is thus defined as either "student + educational level" or "worker + economic sector".

2. Destination Assignment

- Refine the commuting matrix based on activity:
 - i. Filter source-to-target census tract connections to include only target tracts containing at least one relevant unit corresponding to the agent's assigned activity.
- Assign destination census tract utilizing the refined commuting matrix from the previous analysis
- Allocate a specific establishment (economic sector unit or educational institution) by applying probabilistic selection based on relative establishment size within the destination census tract.

3. Working Schedule Assignment

- Determine departure times based on statistical distributions of commuting patterns related to the agent's activity type and destination municipality
- Establish work schedules including shift patterns and weekly working days.

Spain

We merge the information of the current use of the buildings of the cadastral data, with more details thanks to the OSM data. The steps followed can be seen below:

1. Read the OSM data of Spain.
2. Read the cell information data of Spain (Spain cells).
3. Read the geometry data of the provinces.
4. Get all the cadastral buildings from each province
5. For each province:
 - a. Get the OSM data of the province
 - b. Join the OSM data, with variables sector, layerindex, subcategory and geometry, to the cadastral buildings. Therefore, for example, if a building from the cadastral is used for public services, we can distinguish whether it is a school, a hospital, etc.
 - c. Add the cell to each building

Following the completion of this process, we obtain one of the two primary outputs of the synthetic population: a file containing detailed information on the buildings for each province. This output is stored in GeoJSON format, which preserves the geospatial characteristics of each building.

The spatial reference system used is EPSG:2062 for mainland Spain, while EPSG:5635 is used for the Canary Islands to accommodate their specific projection requirements.

The table below lists the attributes included in the buildings file:

Name	Type	Description
reference	numeric	Building id
currentUse	categorical	Current use of the building (info from the cadastral data): '1_residential' '2_agriculture' '3_industrial' '4_1_office', '4_2_retail', '4_3_publicServices'
sector	categorical	Main sector of the building (1, 2 or 3)
LayerIndex	categorical	Classifies the point of interest in 9 layers – 0 – Public facilities such as government offices, post office, police, ... – 1 – Hospitals, pharmacies, ... – 2 – Culture, Leisure, .. – 3 – Restaurants, pubs, cafes, .. – 4 – Hotel, motels, and other places to stay the night – 5 – Supermarkets, bakeries, ... – 6 – Banks and atm – 7 – Tourist information, sights, museums, .. – 8 – Miscellaneous points of interest
Subcategory	categorical	Subcategory of the LayerIndex
value	numeric	Area in square meters
code	category	INE code where the building is
cell_group	category	INE cell where the building is
geometry	geometry	Geometry of the building

Once we have done all the steps needed, we are able to create a synthetic population for Spain.

In this program, as mentioned, we are going to obtain two data sets: one personal data set, with all the information of the people of the province, and another one, a geodata set, with the location of the residential buildings. The steps followed to achieve them are:

1. **Get the residential buildings.** We filter all municipality buildings by selecting only the ones that their current use is residential. After that, we concat all the municipalities in one big data set for the province with the following columns: code, reference (building id), number of dwellings and geometry. Below, we have a description of the data.

Name	Type	Description
code	numeric	Municipality code
reference	numeric	Building ID
numberOfDwellings	int	Number of dwellings of the building
geometry	geometry	Geometry of the building

2. **Dwelling-level expansion.** In this step, we transition from a building-level dataset to a dwelling-level dataset. Initially, each row in the dataset corresponds to a single building. To represent individual dwellings, we expand each building row based on the number of dwellings it contains.

This is achieved by duplicating each building row as many times as the number of dwellings it contains. For example, if a building has 15 dwellings, the corresponding row will be repeated 15 times.

After this transformation, the column originally indicating the total number of dwellings in the building is renamed to `dwelling_id`. This column now represents the index of each dwelling within the building, ranging from 1 to the total number of dwellings. Continuing the previous example, the 15 rows corresponding to a building will have `dwelling_id` values from 1 to 15, representing each individual unit.

This expansion allows the assignment of household-level attributes and enables a more granular modeling of the synthetic population.

Name	Type	Description
code	numeric	Municipality code
reference	numeric	Building ID
dwelling_id	int	Dwelling id inside the building
geometry	geometry	Geometry of the building

3. **Assigning Household Type and Size.** Once the dwelling-level dataset is created, we assign a household type and household size to each dwelling by sampling from the previously generated distributions. This process ensures that the synthetic population aligns closely with observed demographic data at the municipal level. The procedure is as follows:

- **Step-by-Step Method.** For each municipality code, the following steps are performed:

For each **municipality code**, the following steps are performed:

1. **Retrieve Empty Home Ratio**
 - Obtain the ratio of empty dwellings from INE data.
2. **Initialize Tuning Parameters**
 - Set `ratio = 10` and `step = 0.005`, which are used to iteratively adjust the number of empty homes to match the target population size with an acceptable margin of error ($\pm 1\%$).
3. **Initialize Tracking Variables**
 - `simulated_population = 0`: Tracks the simulated total population of the municipality.
 - `n_empty_homes = 0`: Tracks the number of dwellings assigned as empty.
4. **Iterative Adjustment Loop**
 While `simulated_population < real_population * 0.99`:
 - a. **Estimate Number of Empty Homes**
 - Compute:

$$n_empty_homes = ratio * ratio_empty_homes * len(dwelling_in_municipality)$$
 - b. **Assign Empty Dwellings**
 - If `n_empty_homes < total dwellings in the municipality`:
 - Identify the indices of non-empty dwellings.
 - Sample `n = n_empty_homes` dwellings and assign them the household type "empty".
 - c. **Sample Household Type for Occupied Dwellings**
 - Determine the municipality size category (e.g., <5,000; 5,000–10,000; etc.).
 - Re-identify the non-empty dwellings.
 - Sample household types from the corresponding distribution and assign them to the dwellings.
 - d. **Remove Empty Dwellings from the Working Set**
 - e. **Assign Household Sizes**
 - For each household type `i`:
 - Filter dwellings of type `i` within the municipality.
 - Sample household sizes from the corresponding distribution and assign them.

- 8. f. **Update Simulated Population**
 - Add all assigned household sizes to `simulated_population`.
 - Decrease the `ratio` by `step`.
- 9. **Finalize Data**
 - Append the processed municipality dwellings to the province dataset.
 - Remove all dwellings marked as empty.
- 10. **Return Output**
 - Return the full set of dwellings for the province with household types and sizes assigned.

4. **Dwelling-to-Person Expansion.** This step is conceptually similar to the earlier *building-to-dwelling* transformation (Step 2), but now we convert from the *dwelling-level* dataset to a *person-level* dataset. The goal is to represent each individual in the synthetic population with a separate row.

To perform this transformation, we expand each dwelling row based on the value in the household size column, which indicates the number of individuals living in the dwelling.

For example, if a household has 5 residents, the corresponding dwelling row will be duplicated 5 times. A new column, `person_id`, is introduced to indicate the index of each person within the household, ranging from 1 to the total household size.

This expansion allows for assigning individual-level attributes such as age, sex, and activity status in later steps. The resulting dataset includes one row per person and contains the following attributes:

Name	Type	Description
code	numeric	Municipality code
reference	numeric	Building ID
dwelling_id	int	Dwelling id inside the building
household_type	categorical	Type of household (e.g., single family, etc.)
person_id	int	Person ID within the household (1 to household size)
geometry	geometry	Geometry of the building

- 5. Assign age, sex and activity.** Using the sex, age, and activity distributions described in the *Data Preprocessing* section, we assign these attributes to each individual.

For the assignment of age, if data is not available for a specific combination of keys (due to the distributions being derived from microdata segmented by household type, exact age, province, and municipality size) we apply a fallback strategy. In such cases, we iteratively search for the most similar available combination of keys by varying the household type or municipality size until we find a matching distribution. This ensures that all individuals can be assigned an age value even in the absence of exact matches in the original data.

- 6. Add a cell group to the population.** At this stage, each individual in the synthetic population is associated with a municipality code. However, in the case of large urban areas (such as Madrid, Barcelona, or Valencia) this level of granularity is insufficient, as these cities encompass entire municipalities. To enable finer spatial resolution, we incorporate *mobility cells* provided by the INE, which divide the territory into smaller spatial units.

These mobility cells vary in size:

- In major metropolitan areas (e.g., Madrid, Barcelona), they are smaller than the municipality.
- In many cases, they coincide with the municipality boundaries.
- In sparsely populated regions, they may encompass multiple small municipalities.

In addition to spatial subdivision, the INE mobility data provides insight into daily activity flows (namely, where people travel to perform their primary activities (work, study, etc.)). This makes the cell structure an ideal framework for modeling daily mobility in the synthetic population.

To assign a cell to each person, the following steps are performed:

- **Define Spatial Bounds.** Use the `total_bounds` method from the `geopandas` library to extract the minimum and maximum latitude and longitude coordinates of each province's geometry.
- **Load and Restrict Mobility Cells.** Import the national mobility cell dataset and spatially filter it to retain only the cells that fall within the bounding box of the province defined in the previous step.
- **Spatial Join.** Perform a spatial join between the individual-level population data and the filtered mobility cells. This join uses geometric intersection to assign each person to a cell based on their associated building's location. If any individuals are not located within a cell (e.g., due

to edge effects or geometry mismatches), the nearest cell is assigned to them based on proximity.

7. **Assign mobility.** Once each individual has been assigned to a specific mobility cell, we can utilize the mobility data to determine where they will carry out their main daily activity (e.g., work, study).

Using the previously computed mobility distributions (which represent the probabilities of moving from one cell to another) we sample a destination cell for each person. This destination cell indicates the location where the individual's primary activity takes place.

This process ensures that the spatial dynamics of daily movement within the synthetic population reflect realistic commuting and activity patterns observed in the real data.

8. **Assign sector.** For individuals classified as employed, we assign an economic sector in order to later allocate a suitable workplace. This assignment is based on sectoral distributions derived in earlier steps and follows a two-fold approach, depending on the location of the individual's workplace:

- **Inter-Provincial Commuters.** For individuals whose assigned workplace is located in a different province from their residence (as determined by the mobility data), the sector is assigned by sampling from a sector-by-sex distribution. This distribution captures the probability of employment in each sector conditioned on the individual's sex and province.
- **Intra-Provincial Workers.** For individuals who work within their province of residence, we use a more spatially refined distribution: the working sector per region. This distribution incorporates building-level data, specifically the total area of buildings associated with each economic sector within each region. Workers are assigned to sectors proportionally, based on the relative surface area dedicated to each sector in their assigned region.

This dual approach ensures that both demographic factors and spatial-economic characteristics influence the assignment of economic sectors in the synthetic population.

9. **Assign activity place destination.** At this stage, each individual has been assigned a destination cell and a working sector (if applicable). Based on this information, we can now allocate a specific building where each person carries out their main activity. The assignment is performed as follows:

- Workplaces.** For employed individuals, a building is assigned by sampling from a distribution conditioned on the destination cell, economic sector, and building area. For example, if a person works in a cell within Madrid and belongs to the tertiary sector, they will be assigned to a building by sampling from the distribution of buildings in that cell-sector combination, weighted by area.
- Kindergarten Places.** Children under the age of 3 may be assigned to a kindergarten, provided that such facilities exist in their destination cell. If no kindergartens are available in the cell, the child is assumed to remain at home.
- School Places.** Individuals aged between 4 and 17 are assigned to a school building within their destination cell.
- University Places.** Individuals whose main activity is studying and who are over the age of 17 are assigned to a university building within the corresponding cell.

After completing all the aforementioned processing steps, we obtain a final **agent-level dataset** (referred to as the *population matrix*), where each row represents an individual in the synthetic population. This dataset contains the following attributes:

Name	Type	Description
code	numeric	Municipality code
cell	character	INE cell
reference	numeric	Building id
dwelling_id	integer	Dwelling id inside the building
household_type	categorical	Type of household
person_id	integer	Person ID within the household (1 to household size)
age	integer	Age of the person
sex	categorical	Sex of the person
activity	categorical	Activity of the person (work, study, etc.)
cell_group	character	Region (mobility cell) where the individual's dwelling is located.
cell_dest	character	Region (mobility cell) where the individual's Main activity takes place.
ref_dest	character	Building ID of the main activity place

